

ZURO

1972

*The Magazine of the History Society
Umtali Boys' High School*

ZURO 1972

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EDITORIAL

History is a social study of paramount importance to the youth of today. Its use, as G.M. Trevelyan pointed out, is "to train the minds of men by a just contemplation of the past..."; at the same time "the appeal of history is largely imaginative". This subject can be absorbed by people today who are well-informed about current affairs and have plenty of leisure time for contemplation. The historian Collingwood asserts that the purpose of history is self-knowledge and this again is an aim of today's troubled youth.

How can these individuals pursue history? The answer lies in the school history society. Within the structure of such a society the three sections of a historian's work can be fulfilled. These sections are the collection and collation of evidence; the interpretation of the results of research; the exposition of the discoveries and interpretations.

The first, the scientific, part of the historian's study requires work in the field, the libraries and with the people. The U.B.H.S. History Society has taken part in this research from the exploring of ruins to the studying of oral traditions. The Old Umtali, Inyanga and Buhera trips were carried out with this aim and had healthy social and educational side effects. The residents of Umtali, the archives and our own museum yielded information to inspire the imaginations of our members.

Imagination is an essential part of history especially in the interpretation of evidence. Unfortunately the above privileges of historical discovery are restricted to those who are able to go on excursions, but the main contribution of the society is its meetings. Here the interpretations are discussed, the ideas of historians are heard and questioned. Finally, for the expositions of an amateur historian's work our school has this magazine.

G. Roberts.

CHAIRMAN'S REPORT

It is my privilege to report that once again the History Society has had, to use a time-honoured phrase, a successful year. Both our membership and our activities have increased and our reputation has spread outside the realms of Umtali. During the September holidays five members of the Society attended the biennial conference of the Central Africa Historical Association, at which our President, Mr. Barnes, gave a talk on the organisation and running of a History Society. The enthusiasm with which this talk was received is demonstrated by the sale of all past issues of Zuro and of the Jubilee Magazine to Conference members. A suggestion raised at the Conference was that the Society might make contact with similar organisations in Mocambique. The money gained from the sale of Zuro will balance the deficit sustained by the screening of the film "Shangani Patrol" : although a financial loss we feel that the historical value of the film more than compensated for this.

As usual the Society has had a variety of speakers, the only common factor being the universally high standard displayed by them all. Reverend Sells and Mr. Latham lectured on African History. At this point I would like to convey the condolences of the Society to Mrs. Sells on the death of her husband on 7th September. The Hon A.R.W. Stumbles, Speaker of the House of Assembly, was our most distinguished visitor, together with Mr. R. Dickinson from the University, Mr. A.H. Siemers and Mr. D.J. Pilbrough. The latter's talk, an illustrated lecture on the Apollo XI Moon Mission, attracted a great deal of comment.

The Society has organised three excursions in the past year. That to St. Augustine's Mission was both historically interesting and socially enlightening; that to Parliament and the National Archives required particular fortitude in braving a cold morning on the back of the grey truck! The main excursion of the year was to Buhera and the Sabi Tribal Trust Land, a trip which gave the Society the chance to try out its cooking utensils purchased when Kopje House closed down.

I would like to pay tribute to my committee who have been a source of both energy and inspiration during the year. Seward and Bekker,

the latter being appointed in the first term when Futter left the school, have been most efficient, and Roberts has tackled Zuro with a will. I do feel that a permanent U.G.H.S. representative would be beneficial. I must compliment the sub-committee as well, under the Chairmanship of Bekker, for a most active and historically beneficial year's work. Without feeling complacent we can admit to much progress this year : it is up to our successors to build upon and extend the reputation of the Society by continued effort.

P. Welsh.

TREASURER'S REPORT

Speaking generally, the finances of the Society are in a sound state with an overall increase in revenue of \$173.85 as compared to \$118.20 last year.

Fifty three members have paid subscriptions out of a nominal ninety members, slightly less than last year. The reason for this apparent reduction in membership probably lies in the fact that there were only six paid up Girls' School members.

Only one film was ordered by the Society this year: "The Shangani Patrol". The showing ran at a loss of \$18.60 but the historical value of the film more than compensated for this.

Income only just covered expenditure this year and if the Society is to expand the Committee might consider increasing either the cost of Zuro or the subscription rates.

As last year, all surplus monies remaining from excursions or at the end of the year will be put into a camping fund.

INCOME & EXPENDITURE ACCOUNT

<u>CREDIT</u>		<u>DEBIT</u>	
Subscriptions	\$ 26.50	Film	\$32.70
Film	14.10.	Parl. & Archives	22.00
Parliament & Archives		Buhera Excursion	51.00
Excursion	23.00	Anticipated cost of	
Buhera Excursion	65.00	Zuro 1972	53.00
Sale of Zuro at CAHA		Secretaries Expenses	2.79
Conference	20.25	Lecturers fees	8.00
Anticipated sale of		'0' Level prize	4.20
Zuro, 1972	<u>25.00</u>	Expenditure	<u>172.69</u>
	<u>173.85</u>	Excess income over expend.	<u>1.16</u>
			<u>173.85</u>

THE FOLLOWING ARE PAID-UP MEMBERS OF THE SOCIETY

R. Adams*	R. Murphy+
R. Allen+	P. Nicholas
J. Barry	R. Otterson
R. Baxter *+	B. Ouborg
J. Bekker*+	C. Ouborg
T. Carroll	R. Plowes
C. Cloete	G. Robert *+
P. Cochrane	M. Seward*
Mrs. Colqhoun	E. Smith*
R. Davis	P. Springer
D. Geisel	N. Storey
G. Gilmour*	C. Swift*+
M. Grispos	R. Teague
B. Groenewald	I. Tennis
I. Gwyther*+	G. van Leeuwen*
J. Heyns*	P. Weatherdon*
R. Hiles	P. Welsh*
A. Hinwood	G. West*
A. Humphrey	C. Wilson*
P. Jackson	M. Winwood
F. James*	J. Cruger+
N. James*	
F. Lefevre*+	
R. Lucas	* Participated in Parliament and Archives excursion.
S. Luke*+	+ Participated in Excursion to Buhera.
R. Manning	
D. Millar	
T. Millar	
S. Morgan	
D. Morkel*	
M. Morkel*+	
F. Moxham*	

SUB-COMMITTEE REPORT 1971-1972 .

Jan Bekker

As Chairman of the sub-committee I was well supported by members: J. Heyns, E. Smith with R. Adams in the museum. I. Gwyther and P. Welsh also helped in the collection of information on occasions.

The main work of the committee this year has been to interview pioneers to Umtali or relatives of pioneers, with the intention of gaining a vivid interpretation of the early days in Umtali. This was done by visiting the person concerned and talking to them about the early days, usually with a tape-recorder handy. The results of each interview are printed in Zuro.

The following people were interviewed:-

1. The late Reverend Sells;
2. Mr. F. Sargent whose father was a pioneer to Umtali;
3. Miss Maritz, daughter of J.S. Maritz;
4. Miss Cripps, daughter of Lionel Cripps.

In April, Mr. Barnes, Gwyther and myself spent a day going through the historical library at St. Augustine's Mission. Several books containing valuable information on the history of Umtali were found, and our thanks are due to the staff of the Mission for their hospitality.

As was the case last year, E. Smith, J. Heyns and myself spent a few days in the National Archives last holidays. Most of the work was done with the microfilm machine as all the early newspapers are now on microfilm.

This has been the most active year the committee has had since it was started in 1970 and I hope the next committee will maintain this progress.

A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : FRIDAY 11th FEBRUARY.MANICALAND IN THE NINETEENTH CENTURY

By Rev. E.T. Sells

In the early nineteenth century Manicaland was inhabited primarily by the Muponda, the Umtasa and further north the Saunyama (i.e. the people of the Monomotapa as found by the Portuguese and recorded in Livingstone's diaries.) Between the Umtasa and the Saunyama were the Tangwena, who originated in Mocambique but who came over to Inyanga under their Chief, Barwe.

In the 1830's there were three Zulu invasions into Rhodesia : (a) the Shangaans under Shoshangane, whose grandson was Gungunhana, the terror of the Manicas in the latter part of the century; (b) the Angoni under Zwangendaba, who passed through the centre and ended up in Nyasaland. In 1929 Rev. Sells saw many old men with three marks on each side of their forehead: they had apparently been carried away as boys by the Angoni to Nyasaland as slaves. They would have passed through this region in c.1834 as according to Theal they crossed the Zambezi in 1835; (c) the N'debele under Mzilikazi, whose history is well known. They enslaved the Shona people, the word Shona meaning "the dirty people who are disliked".

The Shangaans attacked the Muponda and despite help from the Portuguese (legend has it that the fighting was so fierce that the Portuguese ran out of ammunition and moulded gold into ball for shooting) the Muponda were beaten. Many moved over to Mtoko where they identified themselves with the trouble that came under Gouveia (a Goanese whose name means "he who comes at you with a spear". His correct name was Manuel Antonio de Sousa and he was an estate-owner and ferocious slave trader who terrorised surrounding natives, raided and plundered petty chiefs and married into various clans). The Muponda remain today in the Honde Valley under Chief Mapurudza.

In the eighteenth century a man had come into this section from Buhera called Nyamuvambire (meaning "the person who came from beyond".) A great elephant hunter he sold ivory to the Portuguese; he also taught the people how to make fire. According to one of Chimbadzwa's sons, before this time they had always eaten their meat raw : how true this is one does not know.

Nyamuvambire became so popular that he was invited to take over the chieftainship, and the manner in which this was done is interesting. As in the Old Testament, African custom has it that the act of giving away earth is symbolic of handing over one's land. Apparently Nyauvambire killed an elephant and, as it was a royal animal, called for the knife of the chief so that the chief's meat could be cut off first. After several

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days the knife arrived and as the beast was being cut up so did Nyamuvambire ask for some meat. A portion was thrown to him but it fell to the ground. Nyamuvambire picked it up and immediately accepted the fact that the people had given him their land. In this way he became chief.

He established his headquarters at Bingahuru in the valley of the Gutu near Mr. Watsomba. Before he died he requested that his body be buried straight out as opposed to the traditional method of binding the legs and tying the parts of the body together. "To lay out the body" is the meaning of the word Mutasa and this was in fact the beginning of the tribe itself.

Nyavumbire was succeeded by a succession of chiefs but the one that concerns us is Matida (1847-65). His brother Bvumbi decided that he wanted the chieftainship and rallied his men, causing Matida to flee to Makoni, who promised to protect him. But Bvumbi was not happy as long as Matida was still alive (this is typical of African history : a chief cannot function properly whilst another still holds the articles of office). Bvumbi gathered together cattle and women and offered them to Makoni in return for the release of Matida. Makoni agreed and Matida was told that he was being taken back to see Bvumbi, but once they came near Bingahuru Matida was tied to a tree and a wooden stake was driven into his head and through his body. His teeth fell out and one of his wives, who was standing nearby, gave them to one of the sons, Tendai (the other sons were Mapurudza, Siteya and Charamuka.) Tendai determined he would revenge his father and went first to Makoni, then to the Shangaans where he learnt how to use a bow and arrow. When he returned he got into touch with Saungweme*, a reknowned witchdoctor and obtained the medicine to fight.

The place where Bvumbi lived at Bingahuru is 600' high, 300' of which is sheer rock. Tendai found at the base a woman, wife of Bvumbi, gathering sticks, who told him that he could only get up by ladder and that the passage was strongly guarded. After some talk Tendai found her to be a little flexible and offered to make her his chief wife in return for her support. The woman tied in her bundle of sticks a strong bark-rope and on the night of a beer drink she let down the rope and the four brothers climbed up. Siteya and Charamuka were left to guard the top of the rope whilst Tendai and Maparudza went to the hut of Bvumbi. He was found in a stupor and Tendai shot him through the heart with a bow and arrow.

* Saungweme, a former Shangaan who had deserted, had defriended the Umtasa people. He lived at Leopard Rock until it "exploded" when he moved to Chikadora. Two of his nephews fought for a nearby chief and were offered a wife each as a reward. The wives failed to arrive and they decided
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According to custom he who cut off the head of Bvumbi would be the new chief: Maparudza refused but Tendai did not hesitate. He called out the people and after outlining what had happened explained that he was the rightful chief; that there was no need to fear him. As the custom however was to kill the supporters of the previous chief, the people fled into Mocambique they were later to return in force, but Tendai, with the help of Gouveia, drove them back. There are people of Bvumbi in Umtali today and Maquaniqua was one of his daughters.

In the same year as his accession 1875, Tendai, by way of saying thanks, sent Gouveia a notched elephant tusk in which there was some earth. In so doing he gave his land away. Gouveia took advantage of this and in 1878 Portugal declared this whole section to be within her province and that Gouveia had right to all that was there.

In the 1880's gold came into the picture and the Ophir Co. (Portuguese) inspired renewed interest in the area. Hearing of this a group of miners from Barberton, including Jeffreys and Martiz, and Bishop Knight-Bruce separately, came to Manicaland in 1888 and pegged the Rezende and Penhalonga mines.

On September 15th, 1890, a group that included Colquhoun and Lionel Cripps made a treaty with Mutasa in which he promised to encourage the spread of Christianity in return for £100 per annum or its equivalent in kind. The Portuguese, when they heard of this, were annoyed and arranged a big meeting with Mutasa for 14th November. Forbes, who had been put in
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to go and demand them. Saungweme advised them against it (as a witch doctor he had received his horn of medicine from the water spirits : this horn is still active) but they ignored him. The chief was angry, caught both, cut off their hands and punched out the eyes of one. One of the boys died but the other became a noted nganga. With an invitation from Mutasa he settled on the side of the mountain near Chiremba on the Premier Estate. (According to Fairbridge there was a cave there into which the Shona would go when the Shangaans came and would never come out. Eventually the Shangaans realised that a passage went right through the mountain and that the Shona were escaping that way. They blocked both ends and slaughtered a large number).

The witch doctor lived there until 1890, and his grandson is a minister in the Methodist Church. Saungweme himself was given the north-east portion of Maranke and the people there today claim to be Saungweme as distinct from VaBocha.

charge of Umtali, took 30 to 40 men and scaled the rocky fortress on top of which Mutasa had his kraal. A big argument was in process in that Mutasa denied to Gouveia, Rezende and d'Andrada that he had even made a treaty with the Portuguese. Forbes promptly grabbed the Portuguese and got away before the 200 warriors of Gouveia could intercept them. Mutasa's 2000 warriors merely cheered. The Portuguese were eventually freed by Jameson at Mafeking but ill feeling persists to this day : the Portuguese complained about the recent naming of the Border Post after Forbes.

Europeans began to move into the area and a fortress was constructed with several cannon in case the Portuguese returned, which they did once but in no great force. Rhodes arrived on October, 9th, 1891, crossing the range where the late Sir Ian Wilson lived. The next day he met with the three nurses, signed a cheque for £150 and undertook to order from England the books which the nurses had lost on their walk up from Beira. One of the best descriptions of Rhodes comes from this period : "he was great in success, he was great in failure; he was great in generosity, he was great in friendliness."

How did Rhodes obtain the site on which Old Umtali was built? According to Valentine Saungweme, a grandson of the great chief, Rhodes and Bishop Knight-Bruce asked Saungweme for a suitable place and were told that the witchdoctor at Chiremba had died* and, in accordance with custom the people had moved away and destroyed the huts. They had moved to the north east portion of Maranke which Saungweme had obtained when at the battle of Manga, fought near Mt. Tikwiri at Rusape, he had Chimbadzwa (son of Tendai) had defeated Makoni and had thrown many off the rock.

Rhodes approved of Chiremba and gave instructions to build a police camp and a hospital. The move took place in December, 1891. As is well known the site was moved again in 1896/97 to a position more accessible to the railway line : the new site was laid out on exactly the same plan as the old one. Rhodes gave to Bishop Hartzwell all the remaining buildings of the old township as well as 13,000 acres of land. 10,000 acres were traded back for land elsewhere which explains why there are only 3,000 acres out there now.

Tendai, of Chief Chifambausuku as he came to be called ("the wild animal that walks by night") died in 1902. It is unusual to come across tribal chieftainesses but there were thirteen under Tendai. Where did these Chieftainesses get their strength? They were permitted to gather as many men as they wanted about them and to have children as they

* Refer footnotes on Saungweme.

desired, although if the father of any particular child was known he would have his eyes put out. Maredwa, for example, is said to have put out the eyes of two of her husbands before she finally killed them. These "fatherless children" were all warriors of the chief : if a battle was brewing the chief called on the chieftainesses who sent both these children and her husbands to fight.

Two chieftainesses, Maquaniqua and Chitanga who visited Sabi-Ophir Hill and Old Untali respectively, were both accompanied by 60-70 men who claimed to be their husbands. If the chieftainesses were summoned to Bingahuru the procession would be accompanied by a husband; Scottish dress was later added by Colonel Methuen (the only European to become a headman of the Mutasa) and the band has survived as Mutasa's famed "Skotchikeri", as seen by members of the History Society on their trip into the Tribal Trust Lands last year.

Rev. Sells ended his address with references to the mutupo system and marriage via Shona custom.

THE MUTASA CHIEFTAINSHIP

As constructed by Mr. H. Cripps of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Ref. also NADA, Vol. 2, p.85.

TRIBE: VaManyika

MUTUPO: Shumba

CHIDAU: Mbizi.

- | | | |
|-----|--------------|-------------------------------|
| 1. | Nyamuvambire | (c 1670) |
| 2. | Nyamodoto | (son of No. 1) |
| 3. | Jure | (Apparently killed by Bvumbi) |
| 4. | Pfete | (brother of No. 5) |
| 5. | Mudemberewa | (1845-47, murdered) |
| 6. | Matida | (1847-65, killed by Bvumbi) |
| 7. | Bvumbi | (1865-75, killed by Tendai) |
| 8. | Tendai | (1875-1902) |
| 9. | Chakanyuka | (1902-1910) |
| 10. | Kadzima | (1911-1943) |
| 11. | Chimuriwo | (1943-57) |
| 12. | Mukukudzi | (1957) |
| 13. | Mukandagomwe | (1957-65) |
| 14. | Pafiwa | (1968 -) |

A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : FRIDAY 24th MARCH 1972

THE ROZWI : THEIR RISE AND FALL

Mr. C Latham,
D.C. Buhera

Mr. Latham, essentially an anthropologist as compared to an historian has based his research on legend and tradition although the little literature he has consulted has tended to support his suppositions. He warned at the outset of his address that his theories were contentious and have not yet become widely accepted in Rhodesia.

As early as 700 B.C. he argued, the Sabeans, who had the run of the Red Sea, were trading as far south as Sofala. By mapping the distribution of the Sabaean word "sabe" (or shava) meaning both "man" and "to make a trading journey" it is possible to show contact between the Sabaens and the people of Southern Africa: such words as Shabani, Shaba Hills and Sabi. Furthermore, early Rhodesians were Capoid (a most typical Capoid would have hottentot features) and blood samples have shown a close affinity between the Capoid and Egyptian/Arab people.

At some stage the Sabaean would have established trading posts and this could be the earliest origins of stone buildings in Rhodesia.

From the third to the seventh centuries the Abyssinians gained control of the Indian Ocean but the area around the Red Sea was very much a troubled one with the rise of Islam and attacks from the Persians. The easiest way to escape trouble was to move south and consequently the Abyssinians drifted down the coast. In this way came the second influx, a Caucasoid people similar in racial origin to the Capoids. It is seldom suggested that they came to Rhodesia but Mr. Latham argued that they did just that, moving inland up the waterways and establishing trading centres including a primitive Zimbabwe. Here they settled: a pre-Bantu culture with its own non-Christian religion. They not only became isolated but they severed relations with the north (Rhodesia's first U.D.I.); so they continued until the eleventh century.

It is agreed that the eleventh century saw major expansion at Zimbabwe as well as some of the best building. How is this to be explained? The importation of the yam and cassava had resulted in a population expansion amongst the negroid people of the Congo Basin. Their expansion south, east and west caused an upheaval on the coast and we find moving south a race which was a hybrid of Caucasoid and negroid (mainly the former) with an additional suggestion of Indonesian influence. They settled Madagascar and moved up the waterways into Rhodesia which they overran. They had a religious form of government (their leaders were divine kings) and they were an energetic race, hence the expansion at Zimbabwe. Because of their origins they preferred the cooler areas, hence we find their ruins mainly in the higher cooler areas: Inyanga, Matendere, even the higher spots of Matabeleland.

These people, the forerunner of the Rozwi, called themselves the Karanga, a word which has no meaning in any Bantu language but, the central letters ra could be taken to indicate a northern origin as in

Egypt and Polynesia ra means "the sun". Rozwi can mean either "the destroyer" or "the ruler" and although the ruling caste were diluted by the ruled they tended to cling to the title: even today those who dominate an area refer to themselves as Rozwi.

The main Bantu invasions began in the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries : it is interesting to note that oral geneologies go back to about 1400 but those before that date are very vague. In 1568(a date given by Posselt although no one seems to know why) the MaZimba people came south; a bloodthirsty tribe, they soon conquered the locals who had become lazy, took over Zimbabwe and called themselves the Rozwi. Their greatest leader Changamire was to emerge about a hundred years later.

The conquered tribes, rather than accept MaZimba rule, tended to move north. Chief Mutota, for example, from the Wedza area, sent a slave to find a northern area which was also rich in salt (only slaves ate their sadza without salt, which was obtained by drying goats dung and burning it to ashes). The chief moved from Mbire to Sipolilo where he met with his returning slave who had found some salt pans. Mutota was not told about the escarpment however, and when he suddenly descended over the edge he was convinced that he had lost his chiefly powers and that he was about to die. He had seen baobabs in the distant lowveld and requested that some should be planted at his graveside: eight of them still survive.

The remainder of his people continued into the valley where they set up a separate kingdom. Mutota is the first recorded Mwene mutapa or Monomotapa, the word meaning "one who pillages and destroys". In the sixteenth century the Portuguese made a fundamental error. They tended to support the Monomotapa in the belief that he ruled Rhodesia. The error of their ways was made clear when in 1680 Changamire chased out the Portuguese, so destroying the power of the Monomotapa for ever.

History is vague after this. There was a distinct form of government but most of the time appears to have been spent in struggles for power. The Rozwi themselves moved to Khami and it was here that they were found by the first of the N'guni invaders, Zwangendaba. The Angoni had an easy time of it in Rhodesia - the Rozwi were completely routed - but Zwangendaba had no ambition to rule and he moved on to southern Tanganyika. His victories eased considerably the task of Mzilikazi's N'debele, the events of whose occupation are well known. More interesting is the fact that the defeat of the Shona* (by which name they had come to be known) had been predicted with amazing accuracy by Chaminuka.

*The word Shona is an enigma in that its origin cannot be traced in any
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He prophesied that because their rulers were so corrupt the Shona were to be punished by Mwari (god) who would send first, a race of warriors from the south; secondly another race of people with no knees (referring to the long trousers worn by the Europeans) who would bring fiery animals on rails and who would rapidly gain control over the country. The bulk of the Shona believe today that the Europeans were sent by divine guidance and that if they should leave the Matabele would once again fall upon the Shona.

The Rozwi had proved ineffectual against the N'guni invaders and were scattered all over the country, as they are found today. A witchdoctor is said to have conjured up a mist to enable the Mambo himself to flee to the Buhera District where, accepted by the VaHera people, he settled forty miles north of the present H.Q. There the N'debele impis found him but the Mambo (Tawochipi) enlisted the help of three Europeans (probably Portuguese hunters or traders) and their firearms swayed the balance of the battle in his favour. Tawochipi gained the title Chibambami because he had "banbamed" the N'debele who, incidentally, never returned.

In his last years Tawochipi's children moved to the more healthy climate of Bikita, followed soon after by the Mambo himself although a remnant was left behind. Other branches moved north to Binga and Wanki, to Rusape under Chiduku and to Chipinga under Mutema.

The Rozwi are no longer proud, arrogant rulers. Vassal groups, associated by marriage, claim to be Rozwi, but at the same time many true Rozwi have changed their mutupo and clan names to avoid recrimination by the N'debele; in this way many Rozwi are disguised as VaKorekore, VaManyika, etc. Chief Chireya of the Gokwe District, for example, changed his mutupo from the heart (moyo) which is that of the Rozwi, to shava (eland). The trick worked because, together with an annual present of Nyoka tobacco to the Matabele, he was left in peace.

Why did the Rozwi collapse? - probably because of inadequate communications. There were no roads and the wheel was never invented; therefore each separate clan could set up an autonomous kingdom as soon as it was over the nearest hill, and without gunpowder it was difficult to get them back into the fold. In consequence, the N'debele merely finished them off and the Europeans defeated both.

of the Bantu languages. It probably stems back to the word Saba which provided the name Sena for a small area on the Zambezi near where the Monomotapa settled. This in turn was mistranslated by the Europeans into Shona. An African will never tell you that he is a MaShona.

A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : FRIDAY 9th JUNEPARLIAMENT

Hon. A.R.W. Stumbles

The Hon. A.R.W. Stumbles, Speaker of the House of Assembly, began by outlining the history of the Chairman of the House, for that is what his position really is. Sir Thomas Hungerfoot, the first recognised Speaker, acted as an intermediary between the monarch and parliament : he "spoke" to the king on behalf of the lower house. This often proved a dangerous job; hence the tradition that when a Speaker is newly elected he is taken forcibly by his proposer and seconder to the Chair.

Mr. Stumbles, with a copy of an order paper, outlined parliamentary procedure. At 2.15 p.m. bells toll and members enter. The Sergeant-at-Arms knocks three times, members stand and the speaker enters. He bows to the left, to the right, says prayers, after which procedure begins with notice of bills.

A bill begins in the offices of the Ministry concerned after which it passes to the Cabinet, the Secretary of Parliament and so to the order paper. The First Reading consists of the title of the bill being read out by the Minister after which the Speaker asks, "What date second reading?" At the second reading the Minister, speaking for as long as he likes, explains the need for the bill. When he has finished members who wish to speak are limited to a forty minute discussion on the principles of the bill, to which the Minister has the right to reply. After debate has ended the Speaker calls for the second reading of the bill, and a vote is taken : the "ayes" as opposed to the "noes". The Speaker decides who he thinks "has it" after which any member may call for a division. The bells ring for four minutes and members file in to cast their vote : the "ayes" to the right and the "noes" to the left. Once passed the Second Reading the House passes into Committee and closely examines every clause of the bill after which the Minister moves that the bill be read for a third time.

A similar procedure is followed by the Senate and after the President's signature the bill becomes law.

The Speaker has other tasks; he is particularly busy in the Budget Debate as each Minister explains his estimates. On Private Members Day a Private Member may introduce a bill and if the motion is successful the Minister concerned is honour-bound to do something about it. A Member may also pose a formal question and the Minister has several days to consider his reply.

At 6 p.m. all Government business comes to an end. At 6.55 an adjournment is called after which members may speak for twenty minutes and Ministers have ten minutes to reply. The House adjourns at 7.25p.m.

Mr. Stumbles concluded by describing the activities of the National Historical Association and inviting Society members to join.

A MEETING OF THE HISTORY SOCIETY : FRIDAY 20th JUNE, 1972

APOLLO XI

Mr. D.J. Pilbrough

Mr. Pilbrough watched the launching of the first moon mission as an "official press representative". His slides, together with a lively commentary, had considerable impact on a large and appreciative audience.

The Society is privileged to have been addressed as well by: Mr. R. Dickinson (4th August) who spoke on Sofala, with particular reference to his recent excavation at the mouth of the Save River. A detailed transcript of Mr. Dickinson's talk is being prepared and will be available to members.

Mr. A.H. Siemers (17th August) who described the organisation behind the trips of the Schools Exploration Society with particular reference to the expedition to the Sabi-Lundi Confluence. Mr. Siemers screened a film of one of the earlier Zambesi trips to conclude a most worthwhile and interesting evening.

ON INVESTIGATING RHODESIAN HISTORY

A surmise of an interview with Rev. Sells, with particular reference to the interviewing of Africans. Those present included Mr. Barnes, P. Welsh, J. Bekker, J. Heyns.

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In collecting oral traditions it is necessary to establish the identity and background of the informant. If he is an African this is best done by asking three questions:-

- (a) His mutupo - often translated as "totem" but in fact it is more than this : "totem" is more correctly used in the instance of the American Indian. The mutupo is in part the indication of the clan, similar to the Scottish clan, but also it enters into almost every type of relationship. It describes an intimate relationship yet not so intimate that there cannot be intermarriage.

Examples of the mutupo of different tribes include:

Mutasa	-	Shumba	(lion)
VaJindwi	-	Shoko	(monkey)
VaManyika	-	Mheta	(python)
VaBoche	-	Shava	(eland)

We are getting today a mixture of mutupo outside the clan. The mutupo usually goes to the father but there are instances of individuals who have come from a Shangaan background but have taken the mutupo shumba. This is done mainly because of the benefits this mutupo might bring in a particular situation.

The advantages of knowledge of the mutupo can be seen in an interview conducted by Rev. Sells with an African girl in Salisbury recently. She said she was from Marandellas but her mutupo was shumba. "You're from the Mtoko section, a member of the Mjonda tribe". The girl readily admitted this and when asked how she came to be in Marandellas replied that her father had gone there seeking work.

- (b) His chidau - sub clan

- (c) Zinzi - i.e. where do you come from?

Divisions between the clans have never been clear cut mainly because women were articles of trade: they were frequently passed virtually as bribes (e.g. Sanyangweme and gifts of women to Maranke) Mr. Bernhardt, for example, claims that the VaRozwi inhabited Murahwa's Hill. It may be true that there were VaRozwi women there who brought their pots with them when they were sent up from Fort Victoria. In later days Mutasa's people settled the hill - we know this because some of their descendants remain. In about 1890 they left and moved to an area south of Rusape, possibly because of pressure from other tribes, the Shangaans and Angoni in particular.

The informant must know that you have a slight knowledge of what you are talking about but at the same time do not let it be known that you know a lot about it. There was, for example, a story at Chikore concerning a lion, a cave and a man who later became chief. Rev. Sells sent out his interpreter, Shepherd, who, after some investigation, saw a man digging in his garden. He greeted him courteously and asked if he could borrow a badza and help him. Whilst digging he began to talk. "I've heard this story about a lion and a man. I don't know much about it but I think it is interesting", and he began to recite parts of the story. "No, you have it wrong", interrupted the informant, and the story emerged.

The following day Shepherd went out with the local minister who was able to point out a man who knew the story. Introductions were made and the next day Shepherd approached him again and managed to elicit his version of the story. In this way he learnt that, at a time when there was much division in the area, a young man was taken by lions and lived with them for a year. He returned to become chief and tradition has it that all the chiefs of the area are his sons.

Another principle to emerge from this story was that if you should be corrected, do not argue. Let your informant correct you. It is one means of getting a story started.

Rev. Sells knows Chief Maranke well and has often sat up until 11.00 o'clock at night talking around the fireside, although he is not so vocal now that he is a chief and therefore a custodian. Once, on climbing a mountain to see the stone walls of an old church Shepherd said to Maranke, "Mambo, what is the meaning of the name of the flat rock down there?" The chief dismissed it as "just a name" but the interpreter kept asking. Eventually the chief turned to him in a severe way and said "Young man, don't you ask me another question".

The position of Shepherd has been made difficult by the fact that African custom does not respect a young man unless he can identify himself with that tribe.

In collecting stories, especially those concerning animals, Rev. Sells would tell a story one evening around the fire and wait for the reaction. "No, no". And so the story would emerge. But it is important that the listeners have confidence in you, the investigator. This applies for example, to the Pearce Commission, wherein Commissioners were approaching Africans who don't know them at all, and the response is therefore reticent and reluctant. It is equally true that different tribes keep things from one another.

In any investigation one thing leads to another. If each lead is followed up it is amazing what one can get hold of. The Rhodesia Reprint Library for example, issued "Adventures in Mashonaland" by Rose Blennerhasset and Lucy Sleeman. It included a photograph of a Chieftainess whose name was spelt in a peculiarly Portuguese way - MAQUANIQUA. Church records show it spelt quite differently. Members of Mutasa's tribe said that she ruled territory near the Revue River at the beginning of this century but that she lived in the Imbeza Valley. Further investigations showed that she was the wife of Vumbe. Why then did she remain after Tendai killed Vumbe? The reason is not certain, but her name means "I have been found". Rev. Sells learnt that she had been buried on a plot of land owned by Maritz. The Archives could not reveal how Maritz got hold of the land, but according to his daughter, Stephanie, Rhodes gave him the land as a wedding present. Because he knew about MAQUANIQUA Rev. Sells received an invitation to go to the plot and climb the mountain on which she is buried, but there is little up there. Apparently she died in 1934.

The late Ian Wilson had a story that she called out her men to fight and when some retreated she ran after them with an axe.

Further reference in the book is made to a mysterious "Sister Amiee". Research in the Archives with the Director, Mr. Burke, eventually located a book about the two nurses in South Africa, it revealed that Sister Blennerhasset was born of Irish parents in France and that her middle name was Amiee.

Another example of this principle is supplied by the rebuilding of the Pioneer Cemetery. Few tombstones were marked and thirteen bodies buried outside were said to be suicide cases (later proven by Escourt Palmer who helped to bury them) Rev. Sells was able to name the graves by reference to church records. The suicide cases were moved in but no marks were put on the tombstones. Later the Town council wanted to know where MacDougal was buried - a brief glance at the chart drawn up when the graves were moved supplied the answer.

It is often necessary to record the same story three or four times. An elderly African, for example, son of Chimbadza, who was Commander of Warriors of Mutasa at the battle of Mhanda, is most knowledgeable although unfortunately blind. His story was taped four times and in each telling he added something more. He was asked, for example, to contribute to the argument as to whether the Matabele ever came through here - we know that they did divide territory with the Shangaans. He asked his mother, one of the wives of Chimbadza, who said that the

Matabele had in fact come this way. The locals had guns and hid in caves, fighting when necessary. After two weeks the Matabele left and never came back.

Finally records must be carefully kept - a card index is most suitable. Photographs need careful handling : often an original can be restored by a professional photographer or by the Archives and copies made.

The Society notes with regret the death of Rev. Sells on 7th September, With his passing Umtali, Manicaland and Rhodesia have lost a dedicated historian as well as a devoted minister of the Methodist Church. Our deepest sympathies are conveyed to Mrs. Sells.

AN INTERVIEW WITH MR. F. SARGENT

Those present: Mr. Barnes, J. Bekker, J. Heyns, I Gwyther.

Mr. Sargent's father, after giving a false age, came to South African with the first Cape Mounted and was stationed at Mt. Frere. He came to Rhodesia with the B.S.A. Co. as opposed to the B.S.A. Police : a photograph of him appears in one of the recent Police Gazettes but no one can trace the uniform he is wearing. He was in Salisbury for several years, originally at the same time as Rhodes' visit, before coming to Umtali. His promotion was limited due to his refusal to adopt Catholicism as a religion but he rose to Public Prosecutor and retired as sub-Inspector. Until the day he died he would never turn his back to a window.

The Police Station was a triangular shaped building situated in the same place as it is now. There were a few cells on one side and a flag post in the middle. A large baboon was kept tied to the flag pole with a stopper just below the flag. About 4.30 this huge beast would start raising merry hell until one of the constables went out with a bottle and gave him a strong noggin. Like his masters he would drink until he became paraletic.

If the Police liquor supplies ran low they would go on an inspection of the Indian stores, as the Indians were only allowed one bottle for medicinal purposes. The merchandise would be examined and any liquor confiscated.

The beat of the native constables extended as far as the present site of C.M.E.D. The constables were armed - against lions - and at the end of their beat, which they reached about 5 o'clock, they had to put a stone into a bin to show that they had gone the full distance. The constables soon realised however that it was far safer to persuade some picanins to put a stone in the bin each night for them.

One of the local tailors employed Africans as mobile advertisements to walk up and down Main Street dressed in good quality suits and carrying sandwich boards. In the evening they would return their suits to the tailor and return to the compound (on the site of the present hospital) on their bicycles. The locals kids who disliked these natives intensely because they felt that the Africans were assuming airs, would wait for them at the drift by MacIntosh and Falla, a blacksmith situated where Puzey and Payne is today. The drift had handrails - very convenient for stretching a wire across at shoulder height! One day however a Model A Ford came out of the turning to the Old Cemetery. There was not time to loosen the wire so the kids scattered. The wire ripped the head off the car which swung across the road and into the yard of MacIntosh and Falla ending up not far from where some of the kids were hiding.

For all children's illnesses quinine was the every-ready cure, and much of the time spent in bed was probably due to this quinine as to anything else. For adults of course, whiskey, at five shillings a bottle, was the remedy most often resorted to, and curiously enough George Pauling, the railway engineer, was of the opinion that heavy drinkers escaped the fever more often than did light drinkers or tea-totallers.

The men were very hard but very honest. At one time Fred Sargent's father owned 45 stands in the heart of Salisbury, bought from some poor devils to provide them with enough money to return home. These stands he then resold simply to get his money back. Those who were down and out frequently borrowed money from him and it was repaid without fail, even though it might have been months later.

The first car was a Nash, which belonged to the Railway doctor, Walter Craven, and was followed by several Model A and Model B Fords. "Barmy" Roberts (Barmy in that he was the local Pooh-ba) had a Chev which used to act as the local taxi, used most frequently by honeymoon couples who wanted to cross the Pass. The road, straight up and straight down again, was too severe for the normal wagon. When Robbie Burns, owner of the Christmas Pass Hotel, heard the whips of the wagon drivers (and they could often be heard as far

away as Odzi) he would tell the boys to ring a ship's bell kept especially for the purpose and fetch the extra span of oxen. The bell was only rung once; any more than one stroke and the oxen would put their tails up and disappear, and it could take days to assemble them again. A similar arrangement existed at Dot's Drift over the Sabi where an extra span was required to pull cars through the sand.

Burns, a large, red-headed man, would keep the drivers at the hotel as long as possible before they returned to Salisbury, on the grounds that with their merchandise sold they had much to spend. Often it was a matter of waking them out of their stupor once their money was finished. Alongside them would be the miners who had their gold dust in little pouches; it was not uncommon to see Burns weighing gold dust on his scales. Some of the kids would clamber across the Pass at weekends hoping to see a fight. Burns would shoo them away towards evening and they would hurriedly return and feverishly do their homework as required for Monday morning.

Rhodes Drive and the Maternity Hospital area was the kids favorite shooting ground: kudu, duiker and bushbuck were common. Mrs. Fairbridge, when visiting in First Street, would make a point of leaving before dark to return to her home "Utopia" just north of the Dominican Convent in case there should be lions in the area.

Meikles had an old workhouse situated where Duly's stands today. Of wood and iron construction it held mainly old bills and accounts but the kids found^a large box of cigarette tobacco. Some they sold as a welcome supplement to their pocket money, some they smoked themselves. When it was finished another smaller box was found, but this one contained black powder- gunpowder. The boys here at the time was Daniel Boone, in fact they would go to the cinema with the sole intention of watching the Daniel Boone serial shown before the main film. This powder was put to all kinds of Boone-like uses but it made only a little "poof", never a good "bang". On finding a six inch coupling however, and on acquiring some cement, the young cowpokes dug a hole, put in the coupling, lined and covered the hole with cement but not before packing it with powder. A small reed was left in the covering and the gunpowder trailed off to a safe distance. Just for good measure a six-cylinder Chevrolet crankshaft was laid over the cement. The fuse was lit and the onlookers retired.

The whole town heard the explosion. Fathers came enquiring but no kids were to be found, and when they eventually returned at 5 o'clock they were a picture of innocence. Moreover, they scrounged the whole area but they never found that crankshaft!

Children in those days probably enjoyed life more than do youngsters today because not only were they more free but they had to make their own recreation. Young boys carrying .303 rifles, with pockets full of cartridges and meeting a trooper coming in on horseback would be met simply with the comment "Had any luck, young feller?".

AN INTERVIEW WITH MISS A. CRIPPS

J. Barnes; J. Bekker; J. Heyns; I. Gwyther.

Lionel Cripps (b. 1864), father of Miss Angela Cripps, came to Rhodesia with the Pioneer Column in 1890 and was engaged in prospecting in the Mazoe area. In response to an appeal from Colquhoun who wanted volunteers to bolster Manicaland against the Portuguese, he set out with ten others and Selous as a guide for Umtali (at this stage the settlement was still in the Penhalonga Valley at Fort Hill). The 150 mile journey took nine days and the party arrived three days after the battle of Chua Hill.

On June 4th, with the Portuguese threat diminished, the small corps was disbanded, and in November 1891 Lionel Cripps claimed his Pioneer Rights : a 4,500 acre farm "Cloudlands" in the Vumba Mountains. At the same time he gave the name "Castle Beacon" to the highest point on the ridge. He lived for one year on Cloudlands with Pioneer Paddy O'Toole. He had been very ill while mining at Mazoe and he wanted to regain his strength on the highveld.

In 1892 he returned to Port Elizabeth to see Miss Mary Lovemore but the call of Rhodesia proved strong. In Johannesburg he was found a job by Harry and Fred Barber as a representative of the Manhattan Syndicate : a newly formed consortium interested in buying the farms and mining claims. He was loaned a wagon, cook-boy, drivers, leader and two horses, on the strength of which he married Miss Lovemore in Cape Town. On 6th April, 1893, three weeks later the couple set out for Umtali. On their approach to Fort Victoria, a number of warriors passed their wagon with shields and assegais. The Matabele raids had taken place in the Fort Victoria area.

By the time the Matabele war broke out they were camped on the Gold Belt at Penhalonga. They later moved into huts lent by Mr. Montague and it was here that, on 26th December, their eldest son Lionel John, was born three weeks early. Being Boxing Day, Mr Cripps

had taken his fleetest horse to the races being held in the Main Street of Old Umtali, seven miles away. An African thatcher realised that Mrs. Cripps was in difficulty and called Mr. Orme Morris, who with legs and arms flying, rode the spare horse to call the doctor. The $3\frac{1}{4}$ lb. baby was given little chance of survival by the doctor but Sister Emily Hewitt remained three weeks with Mrs. Cripps and the baby survived. He was baptised at the hospital by Bishop Knight-Bruce.

Lionel Cripps had to return the equipment of the Manhattan Syndicate, including the Xhosa driver Daniel, to Salisbury. This left him with little enough but when teams of oxen began to disappear the townspeople became worried. Eventually an old African told them that he knew where the missing oxen were and Capt. Nesbitt (later V.C.), Joe Nesbitt and Lionel Cripps set out. They lost their saddles crossing the rain-swollen Odzi River but, refitted, continued as far as the lower Wedza region. A village in which the oxen were kraaled was raided at dawn and the beasts recovered but the villagers themselves had got wind of the attack and had disappeared. The huts were burnt, sheep, goats and some native cattle were taken, together with a few prisoners. (Two of the latter escaped at night and the others proved to be of nuisance value only and were released).

The party continued to Salisbury where the High Court compensated him by allowing him to keep the cattle, sheep and goats. The "Avenue Hotel" was so full of bugs that Mr. Cripps left for Umtali at 3 o'clock in the morning. His horse, Jesse, an exceptional mare, covered the distance in $2\frac{1}{2}$ days. Jesse was later sold to Dunbar Moodie for £100, and another horse. This new acquisition unfortunately died and for months Lionel Cripps was seen walking everywhere.

In 1894 the Cripps family moved to "The Park", a farm west from and lower than "Cloudlands". Huts were built, near the gum trees which today stand at the Nyachowa Falls turn off. Going into Old Umtali to sell their produce, Mrs. Cripps and baby on a black donkey and Mr. Cripps in front with a stick, the trio were soon labelled "The Holy Family".

In 1895 the homestead was burnt out and everything was lost, including the belongings of Sister Emily who was staying with them; the child was saved only by the prompt action of a picanin "Pumpkin". The family moved temporarily to Old Umtali and returned to "The Park" to stay only three weeks before Mr. Cannell rode out to the homestead and warned them that Rebellion had broken out. That night the limbo-covered window was "locked" with a toothbrush and next morning

preparations were made to leave. All the belongings were wrapped in cloth whilst Mr. Cripps sought carriers from the local headman, Gondo. An old African remonstrated with Mr. Cripps for leaving to which the pioneer, old in the ways of the native and the bush, replied "when the grass is dry it catches fire quickly".

The time spent in the laager was described by Mrs. Cripps as "The most dismal six months of my life... we had all the discomforts of life in the laager without any of the excitements." After staying for a time with various friends mother and child became ill and on doctor's went to Port Elizabeth. She travelled by mule coach as far as Chimoyo and then by narrow guage train coaches. Lionel Cripps sold his cattle to the Imperial Government (because of the rinderpest they were quickly passed to the butcher) and two months later followed his wife.

Their return coincided with the move of the town over the Pass and they lodged with Dr. Howarth (opposite present-day Forestal House) whilst a wattle-and-daub three roomed house was built on "Cripps Plot" (top of Allan Wilson Avenue). Below them was Mrs. Fisher and Mr. Burnett (sister and brother) and Major Dennison who between them owned most of this area.

Cattle were imported from Australia to replace those lost by rinderpest and were herded by O'Neill on the present site of C.M.E.D., then known as O'Neills Pools. All these cattle died of East Coast Fever and their bones were used by the local farmers as meal.

Harold was born in this house at Umtali but after two years, with Lionel Cripps ill and some money obtained from the vegetables and brickfields, the family decided to make the $2\frac{1}{2}$ days journey along the footpath back to "Cloudlands". A three roomed house was built but in 1900 the incessant rain and the poverty of the natives of the area persuaded the Cripps to move back to "The Park" where the trading store belonging to Clark and Offim had been evacuated.

Hereward, christened by the missionary poet Arthur Shearley Cripps, was born just before Lionel Cripps bought the adjoining farm "Fernhill" for £300. Much hard work was put into the property despite the many setbacks : lions (which came annually) and wild dog : some oranges were grown from seed but the majority were budded onto lemon stock. (these were two very nice groves, all cattle were shot when symptoms of East Coast Fever appeared; an imported bull was taken by lions after only one year; jacals took the turkeys and badgers took the poultry.

Two Angoni cows, taken by the B.S.A.P. in a scuffle in Nyasaland, proved to be excellent cattle and the basis of a herd which was developing when, in 1904, Lionel Cripps was called to London for the Goldfields of Rhodesia. Mrs. Cripps had already presented him with a fourth son and the fifth child, born in 1905, shortly after Mr. Cripps' return from London, proved to be a daughter, Angela.

With father away Jack Tulloch (14) had helped run the farm, although this did not stop young Hereward from burning down the kitchen!

In 1910 Mrs. Cripps was ill and took Angela down to the coast, and in 1914 Lionel Cripps was elected M.P. for Eastern District. (In 1920 Mrs. Tawse Jollie, wife of Colquhoun, was M.P. for Umtali). Because of the war there were no further elections for some time and the annual income of £200 was the family's only reliable source of income.

With the declaration of war, the eldest brothers went to South West Africa and East Africa whilst the remaining two, 14 and 12 years of age, ran the farms at Fernhill and Cloudlands. The only dip was at Fernhill, which meant a fortnightly trek with the cattle, and twice in the war the family moved completely to the lower farm.

Edgar Evans, who had made some money on the Kent Mine, bought Manchester and Mr. Cripps made the road from the present picnic spot at Cloudlands to his farm. Evans' four-seater Ford afforded many an amusement to the children as it became stuck on the steep sandy hills.

Miss Cripps can still remember the war-time fetes held in the town and the agricultural shows held in the Drill Hall.

Mr. Cripps was to become the first speaker of the Rhodesian Parliament and eventually died in Umtali in 1950.

A REPORT ON THE HISTORY SOCIETY EXCURSION OF 27th MARCH, 1972.

Frances James U6

As one approaches St. Augustine's mission, the most imposing building is the chapel, which is just the size of a church. Classrooms and laboratories crowd round the chapel, there is a swimming pool and playing fields can be seen a little further off. The mission occupies almost a complete valley, which is wooded and green, and surrounded by fairly steep bush-covered hills. A greater part of the valley is devoted to a farm which provides a large proportion of the school's food.

The mission is now a complete senior school for Africans, ranging from Form One to the Upper Sixth. Pupils can take 'O' and 'A' level, these examinations being those of the Cambridge Examining Board. Formerly, it was a junior school, but it was one of the first in Rhodesia to gradually grow up until it was capable of taking senior students.

The buildings are very adequate. The church is impressive and made of red brick. Inside there is a high roof and wooden pews, with a special gallery in which sits the choir. The chapel's special pride is its angelus bell, which is mediaeval and was brought over from England to Rhodesia. There are several laboratories, a music room and a domestic science room, as well as two very impressive sixth form study rooms in which each pupil has a cubicle to himself (or herself) in which to keep books and work at their own desk. A light, airy, library looks out over the valley. In this there is a strict rule of silence is enforced and there are tables at which sixth formers are allowed to work.

Both girls and boys work together, the percentage of boys being considerably more than that of girls. The accommodation of the school is divided into four parts. There is the priory, in which the fathers live, where they have their own library, studies and dining room. Next is the complex which is for forms one to four, another for form six and yet another for the two orders of nuns and the girl students.

The mission was founded in 1891 by Bishop Knight Bruce who asked Chief Mutasa for the land on which the buildings now stand. There is also a cemetery on the land, in which is buried a certain John Wilkins, a coloured who was with Livingstone on his Zambezi expedition. He then left the explorer and joined Bishop Knight Bruce who left him to start the mission. Unfortunately, he died quite quickly of blackwater fever.

Originally the Bishop did not envisage the founding of a school, but rather a farm with a sawmill working on the waterfall which interrupts the stream in the valley. In 1890 the mission became one of the first

technical schools in Rhodesia. At first quite a few students came from Malawi and they still come from all over central Africa. The first term that the school had consisted of seven pupils, only three of which stayed on to do their J.C. All of whom had successful careers. In 1917 part of the mission was used for teacher training, now, as well as the school, there is a maternity unit, a hospital, an orphaange and a printing press.

The mission housed the first St. John's Church in Umtali and has since done a great many good works as well as teaching its pupils. In 1918 there was a virulent epidemic of Spanish Flu, during which the school closed down in order that the nuns could bring help to the sick. Two of the brethren still spend their time going round the village preaching the gospel.

Altogether there are 423 pupils, a quarter of whom are girls. There are in fact three religious orders represented on the staff. The priests are from the Community of the Resurrection, a small order which came out to Johannesburg in 1902. There are only about eighty priests in the total community. There are two orders of nuns, an African one which arrived at the mission in 1933, and a European order which came in 1952. Altogether the mission is prosperous and happy, and appears to be fully occupied with its most admirable task.

Our warmest thanks are due to Father Keble Prosser and his Sixth Form students who were our hosts for the afternoon.

VISIT TO THE ARCHIVES AND PARLIAMENT : 23rd AUGUST 1972

Promptly at 6.00 a.m. six girls, seventeen boys and Mr. Barnes left Umtali in the grey truck, destined for Salisbury. The party, breakfasting at Eagles Nest, reached Salisbury at 10.00 a.m. and changed into school uniform at the home of Rachel's parents, Mr. and Mrs. Baxter.

At the National Archives we split into two groups whilst Mr. Barnes handed over a series of photographs and documents collected by the Society. Each group was conducted through the various parts of the building and saw how the records were kept and photographs made. The process of micro-filming was explained to us and the guides, Mr. Barbour and Mrs. Pichanick, had laid out a display of photographs of Umtali's early days. In the gallery we saw the exhibition "Rhodesia Through Books".

Mr. and Mrs. Baxter provided us with a magnificent lunch, after which we drove to Parliament where we were met by the Deputy Secretary, Mr. Eric Caldecourt, who explained to us the functions and proceedings of the House. Seated in the Strangers Gallery in the Assembly we saw the official procession, question time, the first reading of a bill and the House in Committee.

Moving to the Senate we heard the unique manner in which Senators speeches are translated verbatim into English, Shona or Ndebele, depending upon what language is being used by the speaker.

After a sumptuous tea and our questions answered by Mr. Caldecourt we left for home, arriving tired but very happy at 8.15 p.m.

HISTORY SOCIETY TRIP TO BUHERA, SEPTEMBER 1972

MONDAY 4th

Eight boys, four girls, Mr. Barnes and the grey truck packed to the brim left Umtali for Buhera. A wayward bumper and exhaust pipe enabled Cruger to display his genius for repair using odd bits of wire, but by 11 o'clock we were at our first port of call, Dorowa. A guided tour of the quarry and extraction plant was followed by lunch and drinks at the club in which Mr Latham, presently District Commissioner Marandellas, refreshed us on the background of the WaRozwi people. We met as well our friend, guide and counsellor for the next five days, Mr. Bickersteth, District Commissioner, Buhera.

We stopped at a beerhall (for informative purposes only) and St. Richards Mission, the latter a most impressive hospitalised outpost staffed by two Irish nurse/missionaries. Buhera itself was a most welcome sight at 5 o'clock and a braai enabled us to meet the members of that excellent little community : almost all of the residents are attached in some way to the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

The girls bedded down in the D.C.'s house and the boys in an attached guest cottage.

TUESDAY 5th

Essentially a 'briefing' day as the D.C. explained the nature of his work in the Sabi T.T.L. Visits to the B.S.A.P. and the Rural Hospital were followed by a most interesting hour in the D.C.'s court and participation in a meeting of the Ku edza Y.F.C.

Tea and tennis preceeded the accepted evening pastimes of drinks and darts.

WEDNESDAY 6th

One of the cadets acted as guide as we visited first the Buhera dip, secondly the Munyira School, which the headmaster kindly opened for our benefit. The afternoon was taken up by the climbing of Gombe and the measurement of a solitary wall on the northern edge. The collection of oral tradition concerning this structure will, we hope, form the basis of a further trip to Buhera later in the term.

THURSDAY 7th

The truck was packed and we began our two day return journey via Birchenough Bridge. The first stop was at a cattle sale at Mharadzano, followed by visits to a Council Hall and a talk by the Secretary, to Matendere Ruins and to the lesser known Muchuchu Ruins. A mobile trek through the bush and a successful search for rock-paintings preceeded our arrival at Mafaruse Rest Camp where one half of the party played baseball-in-the-maizelands whilst the other half wrote up their diaries or went with the messengers on a fruitless search for a sheep which could be braaied.

FRIDAY 8th

A brief stop at Chief Nyashanu's grave was followed by a more lengthy visit to the "tree-with-no-name" and a typical African kraal. After being "kippered" in the huts of the kraalhead's various wives we were quite happy to scramble once more on to the truck and drive to the hollow baobab on the banks of the Devuli River and to the Devuli Irrigation Scheme. A conducted tour by the manager, Mr Sparrow, and lunch at Chamutsa Rest Camp was followed by a swim in the pool at Birchenough Bridge Hotel. After bidding farewell to Mr. Bickersteth we set out on the last leg of our journey, a tired party but one with a storeful of happy memories, experiences and stories to be countlessly retold.

We would like to extend our grateful thanks to Mr. Bickersteth, who did so much to make the trip the success it was; to Mrs. Bickersteth, who gave up her kitchen to our cooks and who tolerated all disruption so cheerfully; to the many people who gave up their time for us, especially Mr. Mills of Dorowa Mines, the Sisters of St. Richards, the member-in-charge Buhera, Mr. Sparrow, and members of the Ministry of Internal Affairs at Buhera; to Veronica Reynolds who was i.c. cuisine, and to the cooks and slaves who co-operated so enthusiastically.

The following essay, together with one by R. Simpson, also written when in 2A, was submitted to the C.A.H.A. Essay Competition, receiving a subsidiary prize and special mention from the judges.

Unfortunately the many excellent maps and illustrations have had to be omitted.

THE FOUNDATION OF THE N'DEBELE NATION

R. Knight 2A

Introduction

The history of the Ndebele Nation in Rhodesia can be traced with the history of its founder, Mzilikazi. Mzilikazi, a military genius under Tshaka led the remains of his Kumalo clan through the heart of Africa to form a tribe numbering up to 60,000 in Rhodesia.

He was also very sound politically and was quick to realize who his enemies were and with whom he could profitably make friends. Thus we can see how a mighty nation was built by a truly remarkable man.

Childhood

"Mzilikazi" means "the great abstainer" or "the path of blood". His father was Matshobana of the Kumalo group under Dividi of the Ndwandwe. His mother was Nompetu who was the daughter of the right hand wife of Dividi. He was therefore a grandson of Dividi.

When Dividi was conquered by Tshaka Mzilikazi soon became an induna. In 1822 Tshaka and Mzilikazi went on a raid against a Swazi tribe. The raid was so successful that Mzilikazi decided to keep some cattle for himself. Tshaka soon found out and this was the real turning point in Mzilikazi's future. So he left to escape punishment.

Mfecani (explosion) 1819-28.

Chaka (or Tshaka or Shaka)

Chaka was probably born in 1787. The word Chaka means "Intestinal beetle" the word his uncle gave him because he was illegitimate. Chaka had a quarrel with his father the chief of the Zulu and joined the Mtwetwe, a tribe who were subject to the Zulu.

He was made an officer after a long time. Dividi captured and killed Dingaswayo (Chaka's father had died leaving him Chief of the Zulu) reorganised the Mtwetwe, joined them to the Zulu and took over leadership.

Military Tactics

His idea was to put all the old men and poor fighters at the so called head of the attack, so giving the impression of a weak army. Meanwhile, the loins and horns (the best warriors) were concealed. When the enemy attacked the head the horns would close up and so encircle the enemy.

Chaka also invented the stabbing assegai (Ixwa).

Assegai

This assegai was made to Chaka's specifications. The shape, weight and balance of each one was tested by him. Chaka's bloodshed caused people to move away from him. An example of his brutal bloodshed when his mother Nandi died he ordered ten thousand warriors to be killed. This bloodshed also led to his eventual murder by his half-brothers Dingaan and Nhlanguana. After the murder Dingaan murdered Nhlanguana leaving him undisputed chief of the Zulu nation.

Mzilikazi's Journey and Mfecani

After escaping from Zululand Mzilikazi (now twenty seven years old) fled to the hills to the South of the Kumalo homeland at a place called Entubeni.

Chaka's troops found him and entering his stronghold nearly succeeded in catching him. But he got away with a few hundred of his men and became a wanderer for fifteen years, living by raiding and stealing cattle.

He moved frequently only spent part of a season in one place. But he did stay for two or three years near the upper Oliphants river in what is now the Ermelo district at a place which they called Ekupumuleni (the place of rest) while they were here they raided all the nearby Sotho tribes killing the men, keeping the cattle and including the women as carriers of the future generation.

The original tribe was joined in 1826 by another and much larger group of Ndwandwe and other tribes, e.g. Dloedeos, old escaped Mtwetwas, Ndlovus, Gumedes and others.

Shoshangana

At about the same time as Mzilikazi fled from Chaka so did four other chiefs. The first was Shoshangana with his tribe the Mzumalo or Shangaans. They fled to the Gaza plains where they were troubled by Chaka's impis and so he and his tribe cleared up and went to the middle Sabi.

Zwangendaba

He fled from Chaka just after Shoshangana. He was the chief of the Kumalo before he moved. At first he followed in Shoshangana's tracks until he got to the Gaza Plains. Here he branched off and went to the Lobombo mountains. Here he had to fight Mzilikazi when he had arrived at Bulawayo and so he fled to where Rusape is now where Mzilikazi's impis attacked again. He fled for the last time to the area of Lake Malawi.

Moshesh He fled from Chaka late in 1824. Moshesh the chief of the Basutu and went to live on the top of a hill called Thababosigo.

By 1825 Mzilikazi was prospering. In 1829 traders like Robert Schoon and William Macluckies wandered north. Mzilikazi received them well.

They were appalled at the condition of the lesser Sotho. This made him want to open up the world. Mzilikazi sent ambassadors 270 miles to look for English settlements.

Soon they came across Robert Moffat's missionary station on the Marico River. Moffat agreed to accompany the ambassadors to Mzilikazi.

After a long stay Moffat eventually left with pressing invitations to return.

But Moffat was never to meet Mzilikazi in this part of the country again, (in a village on the side of modern Pretoria).

In April 1830 a raiding Zulu regiment swept through Mzilikazi's kingdom. The next year the Griquas also attacked.

In 1832 a boisterous Zulu army attacked Mzilikazi. The result was complete shambles and Mzilikazi fled to the Marico valley. In August 1832 Mzilikazi fell upon the unfortunate Hurutshe tribe. They were promptly ejected while their livestock and women were siezed. So Mzilikazi called this place Cabeni (the place of confidence). In 1835 Moffat made his second visit to Mzilikazi and this time he was received like a long lost brother. Moffat told him of some French Missionaries who would like to settle. And in 1836 they arrived. Mncumbati (who had been sent to examine the white man's world) came back with a present to Mzilikazi from the Governor Sir Benjamin D'urban. All Mzilikazi wanted now was peace and quiet.

On 24th August 1836 the Ndebele attacked a voortrekker party of Stephanus Erasmus and killed four Europeans. Nearby on the banks of the Vaal River a second party was attacked. Twelve Europeans were killed and four captured. These were two men and two tiny girls. One of the men was never seen again and the other returned to the English. One of the girls died of tetnus and the other was the girl called Sarah Liedenburg who took Lobengula to safety.

In December 1836 Mzilikazi attacked Potgieter and captured five thousand cattle, fifty thousand sheep, plus all of the horses there, while Potgieter was out exploring and hunting. (he did this just to show that he owned this land and he did not like people trespassing on it without asking him).

In June 1837 Potgieter with two hundred men under him attacked Mzilikazi. They rounded up seven thousand cattle and went away. In July 1837 the Zulus arrived and attacked the so called iziphangele

(weaker tribes) and flattened them to the last man. On the first of November 1837, the Voortrekkers attacked again.

This time Mzilikazi was chased Northwards through the bush for nine days.

The crushed Ndebele now settled down for a few years hunting and wandering around painfully putting themselves together again. Now Mzilikazi took the area of the Nonbya people. The disadvantage of this area was the presence of the tsetse fly. It was now that Mzilikazi heard that his presumed dead son Nkulumane had become king of the other half of his tribe which had fled in another direction when the Voortrekkers chased them. So Mzilikazi led his people up the tributary of the Gwaai River known as the Bembezi (the unpleasant one) He informed them he was coming and they immediately confessed that they thought he was dead.

Eventually they united again. Mzilikazi admitted it was a lovely place; this would be his new homeland (Matebeleland usually misspelt Matabeleland).

Mzilikazi ordered Nkulamane to be put to death and once he was out of the way he put all Nkulamane indunas on a hill and told them they only were suitable enough to give thanks to M'wari for delivering them to this lovely place. Then when they were in the middle of the service he ordered everybody to be killed who was on the hill. This caused a great amount of ill feeling amongst the followers of Nkulamane which was to cause great trouble further on in the history of Mzilikazi.

The Ndebele Domain

Mzilikazi now built himself a new capital called Hlahbandlele. The site, near the upper Mudyangwani, was both handsome and strategic. The Ndebele had not the slightest problem in taking the land. The Warozwi did not even try to resist as they had previously (about three months ago) been beaten by Zwangendaba and the Nxmalu. Their last Mambo Djiri Mutinhima simply fled to the east. His descendants may be found living in a much more reduced state in the Bikita district of Rhodesia nowadays. Zwangendaba had already left the country and Shoshangana was keeping quiet in the south.

Nxaba (another scion of the Zwidi tribe or Ndwandwe) also left Rhodesia. His travels came to a stop on the banks of the Zambezi River where he was murdered at a dinner party.

With both Zwangendaba and Nxaba out of the way Mzilikazi claimed the land as his. The Karanga and Warozwi cringed beneath the reputation of the Ndebele warriors.

Mzilikazi very soon organised his new domain into a properly governed state. He divided Matabeleland into tribal divisions. In each division there was a garrison of warriors, a place for the king to stay and one of his wives. West of the capital was erosion on such a massive scale it had washed away a fifty mile long jumble of 5,000' mountain. Mzilikazi gave them a name (Matobo) the bald heads, which is a name really fitting to this freak in nature.

Immediately north and west of the Matobo are the divisions of the Ndebele known as the igapha (the inner area) and the Nhlope (the white area). This section was under the council of Magquekeni Sithole (a former Zulu aristocrat now of the Ndebele). The regiment garrisoning this area were the Nyamyindlovu (flesh of the elephants). This regiment had also the job of looking after Mzilikazi's so called game park which was on the site of the Kruger National Park now. This is where he did a lot of hunting which was his favourite passtime.

The division of the Ndebele which had accompanied Nkulamane, the Mnjame (black) were settled in the eastern part of Mzilikazi's domain. The commander who replaced Nkulamane was Mgijijili Gwebu and under him were some of the most important amakhanda (military headquarters).

The fourth division of Ndebeleland was amabutho (the regiments). This was the main military training ground with several garrison centreset places like kwazwangendaba (the place of Zwangendaba) where he had stopped once before.

The voortrekkers had by no means forgotten Mzilikazi. And in June 1847 Potgieter ntheleka (the attacker) rode up with two hundred and thirty three men. North of the Limpopo an Ndebele tribe came across one of Potgieter's camps when they were out. The Ndebele attacked killing sixty servants and scattering the few Europeans that were there at the time. Potgieter turned in his tracks and chased after the Ndebele who fled to the Matobo to a place called Manyoni (the hill of the birds).

Potgieter led his men right through the Matobo. Their route is still remembered as ekhalweni lu ka Ntheleka (the pass of Hendrick Potgieter). He got all the way to Mzilikazi's inner sanctuary, but the Ndebele harrassed them at night. Because Potgieter had not suitable means of attack he turned for home.

In 1848 Mzilikazi sent ambassadors to Potgieter's settlement to make peace. In 1852 Potgieter sent a commission under J.G. Bronkhorst up to see Mzilikazi. They discussed the terms of the treaty and afterwards Mzilikazi sent Maropa an ambassador of his to go and sign it with Potgieter.

When they arrived they found Potgieter dying and on the 16th of December 1852, he died before they had signed it. However, his son and Potgieter's successor Pieters signed it in the presence of the Ndebele warriors on the 8th January, 1953.

After this Mzilikazi was quiet at peace for the rest of his days. The voortrekkers blocked the Zulu's, the Portuguese, Karanga and WaRozwi were peaceful and Shoshangane was minding his own affairs.

He died on the 9th September 1868 at Enquameni and was buried on the 9th November in a cave at Mtumbane eight miles south of the royal capital Nhlahlandela.

Character.

In the Ndebele nation there were Zulu, Swazi, Sutu, Kalanga, Shona and all sorts of different tribes not bound by any religious or spiritual link. Their god was their nation and their prophet was Mzilikazi.

This was the power which he had over his thousands. He had a mystical personality which even a century after his death is still living. His memory is still revered and few white writers can say much against him.

Great men are always lonely and Mzilikazi was no exception. They accept praise from lesser men but all too often have no one to admire. When Mzilikazi met a man who did not pay extravagant compliments, who did not always do as Mzilikazi wished Mzilikazi fell for him. This man was Moffat.

Mzilikazi ruled his massive domain by pure feat. There was no other way for him. He kept himself clear of white men on the whole. It was not that he disliked white men on principle, Robert Moffat he adored, Morgan Thomas and John Lee were especially favoured but generally whites were not welcomed at his court and Boers were not even allowed on his land.

The death of Mzilikazi inevitably released some very mixed emotions. The tribes that had been plundered by Mzilikazi and his regiments were of course delighted. The Europeans hunters and missionaries were very disappointed and sad as he had been a great friend of theirs.

So a great argument arose about Nkulamane who was the rightful heir. Nkulamane supporters flatly refused to believe that he was dead. There were even rumours that he had been exiled back to Zululand. This is where Lobengula comes into the picture.

Lobengula

He was probably born about 1833 in the Northern Transvaal. His mother was a Swazi princess who had been captured on a raid. This meant that Lobengula was not a true Kumalo (full blooded Matabele) and this is why so many of the Matabele were reluctant to accept him as king. When

he was about ten years old he was kidnapped (or rather saved from certain death) by the captured girl Sarah Liedenburg who was now about eighteen years old. She took him to M'wari (M'limo) in the Matopos who looked after him. This meant he was fleeing from the Ndebele and his father for most of his life and he relied mostly on the whites for support.

The indunas of Mzilikazi began following up the rumours of Nkulamane's supposed flight. In the middle of this Lobengula arrived and told them to keep on searching because it would mean certain death for Lobengula and his indunas if Nkulamane suddenly pitched up. However, after two years of fruitless searching Lobengula was proclaimed king.

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 "To the Banks of the Zambezi" by Bulpin Pages 7 - 14
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HISTORY SOCIETY COMMITTEE

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HISITORY SOCIETY QUIZ

The quiz was won this year by Crawford with 48 points (Welsh 31 points) followed by Palmer with 35 points (Roberts 24) Livingston and Hill.

(A synopsis of one chapter of the Sub-Committee's research)

Most people are aware that Umtali was moved from Old Umtali to its present site because of the difficulties in bringing the railway over the Mutarandanda Range. What is not so well known is that the site of Old Umtali was not itself the original settlement: that distinction belongs to an area immediately south of Penhalonga centred on Fort Hill.

No discussion of the establishment of a settlement in the eastern mountains can ignore the activities of the Portuguese in the area. In the late nineteenth century Portugal exercised a rather shadowy administration over Manicaland, her authority resting in the powers of such individuals as Manuel de Sousa (Gouveia) - a prazo-holder living on Gorongosa mountain with a large number of African retainers - and Major Paiva d'Andrada, an energetic soldier who, in 1888, had obtained permission from his government to develop mineral and commercial schemes in the 'interior'. D'Andrada's "Companhia de Mocambique" edged its way up the Pungwe River and across country to the Revue river where a fortified settlement was erected over an old site at "Massi Kessi" to serve as company headquarters. The "Companhia" however, severely short of funds, decided to lease out mining concessions to individual speculators. Such a lease was signed with Mr. J.H. Jeffreys.

Jeffreys had joined in the Barberton goldrush of 1883, but, disillusioned like so many others, he began to look around for other ventures. Hearing of the formation of the Companhia de Mocambique he and some friends, in 1888, obtained a concession from the Portuguese and formed a syndicate. Jeffreys left for Beira, meeting on the way J.S. Maritz at Lourenço Marques and Baron Joa Rezende, the latter having recently been appointed manager of the Companhia. After some difficulty in obtaining sufficient carriers due to the raids on Manicaland of Chief Gungunhana, Jeffreys, Maritz, Rezende and nine others set out for Macequece. The difficulties of the Pungwe route meant that Rezende and Jeffreys eventually continued alone until they reached the fort, to which they were confined by persistent rain. During a few dry spells Jeffreys explored as far as Mutasa's kraal, but, suffering badly from malaria, he was compelled to return to Beira three months later.

In August 1889, Jeffreys travelled again to the fort where he met up with Maritz and the nine men of the original party. In October he pegged two mines, naming one after Baron Rezende and the other after Count Penhalonga of Lisbon. Sailing to London Jeffreys sold the Rezende to a Company but formed a syndicate to work the Penhalonga: work in fact started under Jeffreys' direction late in 1891.

In 1890 a series of miners - English, French and even a native of Jersey - had entered Manicaland by arrangement with the Portuguese. A border dispute however was brewing. For more than three centuries the Portuguese had had the opportunity of establishing colonies in Mocambique but had done little, although the personal efforts of d'Andrada had resulted in a flag-raising ceremony at Mutasa's kraal in 1889. In Bechuanaland the Pioneer Column was assembling, with instructions from Rhodes to occupy the eastern highlands and, if possible, to establish a corridor to the sea. Consequently, on 3rd September 1890, Jameson, Colquhoun, Selous and an escort of seven mounted men left the Column for Manicaland.

Jameson was thrown from his horse and, with three broken ribs, was forced to rejoin the Column. On 12th September (the same day as the Column reached Salisbury) Colquhoun and Selous reached the Mutare River and established their camp under a fine shady tree midway up a hill slope near the Bartissol mining camp. This site, at present that of the Pioneer Nurses Memorial, can be considered as the nucleus of the first Umtali.

Two days later a party visited Mutasa. Impressed by rumours of the strength of the Pioneer Column, the chief was quick to sign a treaty pre-prepared by Colquhoun in which he gave considerable mining and concession rights to the Company and promised to grant no concession of land to either parties. The Company promised in return to assist in the propagation of Christianity and in the education of the natives and to pay an annual subsidy of £100 per annum.

Colquhoun left for Salisbury to take up his post as Administrator of Rhodesia, leaving behind him at Mutasa's kraal an excellent linguist, Mr. Trevor, a sharp, semi-civilised native named Jonas, and a promise that a police detachment would be sent down as soon as possible with the first payment of the subsidy. Sergeant Major Montgomery and four men of "B" troop were sent from Salisbury as an advanced guard, followed on 27th October by 10 of the B.S.A. Co.

Police under Lieutenants Graham and Shepstone. Captain Forbes left Salisbury four days later with orders to assume supreme command, to occupy as much territory as possible and to secure further concessions eastwards. On arrival in Umtali he was made aware of Portuguese attempts to recapture the allegiance of Mutasa, by force if it proved necessary.

On November 8th Gouveia entered Mutasa's kraal and raised once again the Portuguese flag. Forbes was placed in a predicament - with only 21 men he could hardly counter the provocative nature of the Portuguese - but help was to arrive from unexpected quarters. First, Denis Doyle, sent by Colquhoun to advise Forbes on native affairs, brought the news that reinforcements could be expected from Fort Charter in about five days time. Secondly, Colquhoun had decided to reinforce the military occupation of Manicaland with a body of prospectors: they were to be the pioneers of a permanent settlement. Consequently, Henry Montague, mining in the Hartley District, was asked to get some prospectors and "drift" into Umtali. His forty men, each supplied with 200 rounds of ammunition, arrived in Umtali at the same time as d'Andrada and Rezende moved into Mutasa's kraal, threatening to "eat him up" (a threat not to be taken lightly) if he did not repudiate his treaty with the B.S.A. Co.

On 15th November, 1890, Forbes and his men stormed the citadel. Achieving complete surprise, Rezende, d'Andrada and Gouveia were arrested: Rezende was released on parole but the other two were taken under escort to Salisbury and transported to Cape Town.

This dramatic victory was a terrific boost to the Company's prestige, but spirits were dampened when news was received that on 14th November a "modus vivendi" had been signed in Europe to the effect that the Sabi River would be recognised as the temporary boundary.

The Company however refused to hand over Manicaland on the grounds that the concession with Mutasa had been signed before the arrangement with the Portuguese.

With the excitement apparently over, the population of Umtali thinned out and when Tulloch arrived in December it had dropped from sixty to eleven, most having drifted back to Salisbury. They left behind them the unmistakable signs of settlement: on one side of the river, on Sabi-Ophir Hill, stood the hut of Mr. Campion, and the

remains of Colquhoun's camp; on the other side, on what is now known as Fort Hill, were the Police lines and the scanty huts of the Company men. There is some controversy as to the date of the actual building of the fort itself : it may have been in November, but, as will be discussed later, it was more likely to have been in May, 1891. Forbes himself marched on Beira but after receiving news of the 'modus vivendi' he was recalled to Salisbury. He left in Umtali Captain Heyman and a small contingent of B.S.A. Co. Police with orders to protect Mutasa and to safeguard Company rights in Manicaland.

The wet season of 1890 was, throughout South Africa, the heaviest in the memory of man, and it caught the pioneers and the Company officials completely unprepared. Malaria was rife; the staple diet was millet meals and pumpkin; clothes and boots were soon worn out (the famous Rhodesian "shorts" were born as men cut off the legs of their trousers to patch the seat, although most did their prospecting naked to save wear and tear on their only pair of pants;) ill constructed huts gave little protection against the rain and all mail was suspended.

During a break in the downpour Tyndale Biscoe and Montague blazed a route over the Mutarandanda Range. Captain Bruce and a party of B.S.A. Co. Police were sent afterwards to cut the road and when they camped on the ridge on Christmas Day a name for the pass was born.

As the prolific rains ended so did interest in Manicaland revive. The arrest of d'Andrada and Gouveia had provoked a storm in their home country and Portuguese volunteers began to gather at the mouth of the Pungwe thirsting for revenge. Colquhoun, determined to thicken the white population of his eastern borders, called once again for volunteers and in May, 1891, a party of ten left Salisbury with Selous as their guide. Amongst their number was Lionel Cripps.

Before they arrived an interesting development took place near Macequece. Heyman had placed his police on Chua Hill, some two miles from Macequece and controlling the approaches to Mutasa's kraal. The fort, which had been evacuated on 24th April on instructions from Rhodes, was jubilantly reoccupied by a mixed force under Col. Ferreira and Capt. Bettencourt. Under flags of truce each side inspected the strengths and defences of the other, until, on 11th May, 1891, the Portuguese sallied forth. With their overwhelming odds they were confident of victory and the resulting battle had much about it that is ludicrous. Nevertheless a lucky shot from the seven-pounder and the accurate shooting of the pioneers and police caused the 300 black Portuguese troops to break, leaving twenty dead behind them. The

patriotism of the 150 white troops faded and absolute panic ensued; the Portuguese officers strolled dejected from the battlefield pausing only to raise their hats to the British before they disappeared.

The fort was looted by the Company men, their booty consisting mainly of forty demijohns of wine. A few mounted men under Fiennes pursued the fleeing Portuguese but at Chimoio they met up with Bishop Knight-Bruce (on his second visit to Mashonaland but his first up the Pungwe) who revealed that orders were being brought for the withdrawal of the B.S.A. Co. from Macequece.

The border dispute was ended on 3rd July, 1891, when the boundary was pushed to 33° East and Manicaland was confirmed as belonging to the Company.

Three days after the Battle of Chua Hill, Lionel Cripps and his party arrived at the Police Camp in Umtali. Cripps, who was later to become speaker of the House of Parliament, wrote that the day after their arrival they helped a few prospectors to build Fort Hill, an excavation dug into the top of the hill with defence walls and placements for cannon. The nine guns taken from the Portuguese presented a formidable appearance but were useless in that the pins had been removed before capture. The remains of the fort can still be seen immediately south of Penhalonga village.

Bishop Knight-Bruce, appointed Bishop of Mashonaland in January, arrived at the settlement on July 1st. A man of tremendous energy, he set out the following day to find a suitable site for a hospital for the three nurses whom he knew to be on their way up the Pungwe River. Instead he came across an area ideal for what he called a "Central Mission Station" (the present site of St. Augustine's Mission) - high land facing west, with water and good soil. Five days later Knight-Bruce and Fiennes visited Mutasa and gained his approval for building to begin. The Bishop also offered the chief the services of a "teacher" to "teach the people about God", an offer which Mutasa was later to accept. 3,000 acres were, with Company permission, eventually pegged, intended not as a farm for the mission as is sometimes supposed but as a reserve should the natives ever be crowded out of their land. A month later the Bishop moved into his quarters.

On 14th July, their feet wrapped in bandages, Nurses Rose Blennerhasset, Lucy Sleeman and Sister Welby arrived in Umtali: their 140 mile walk from Mupand's on the Pungwe had taken 15 days. The

situation was far from bright : the nurses had had to leave many of their precious possessions on the trail, the stores looted from Fort Macequece were running out and Sister Rose, stricken with fever, was running a temperature of 105° . Temporary accommodation was available beneath the fig tree in a hut belonging to Mr. Campion, manager of the Sabi-Qhir Mining Co., and the Bishop set about organising a hospital and permanent huts for the nurses nearer his mission, although the site was later to be moved to within fifty yards of the Police lines.

The nurses recovered little of what they had left on the trail. Mr. Sutton, who had been left in charge at Chimoio, went down with fever and whilst helpless in his shelter some white men arrived, pronounced him to be "doasid dicky" and not likely to "pull out", helped themselves to his food, knife, kettle and other appliances, and left him to his fate. Fortunately, his carriers from Umtali arrived the next day and helped him on his way to the settlement.

Following the nurses came the Bishop's servant, a Coloured, John Wilkins; a carpenter by trade, he had travelled with Livingstone and had many delightful tales to tell of his journeys. Wilkins was to die in February of the following year and is buried at St. Augustine's mission. Another of the many tragedies of those times befell a Dr. Glanville, who had joined with the nurses on the journey up the Pungwe; he set out for Salisbury but was found dead in his blankets a few miles short of his destination and was buried where he lay.

In August the nurses took possession of their new huts which had been furnished from the spoils of Macequece and included a real table, chairs and a bath. The encampment was enclosed by a low wall of lossely piled stones, the ineffectiveness of which was clearly demonstrated when a hyena was found in the store hut trying to get at a piece of ox suspended from the roof.

August saw as well the arrival of Mrs. "Sandy" Tulloch who had walked the same route as the nurses whilst her children were carried in manchillas. En route Mrs. Tulloch had met up with Mr. Platnauer who, with seventy carriers, was on his way to start the store which was later to become the Manica Trading Company.

Lions were a constant source of worry but it was popularly believed that a lion would not take a man when he could get a bullock and that he preferred a native to a whiteman. This illusion was dispelled by the accident that befell Mr. Teal. Mr. Teal went out prospecting, taking with him a native servant, a wagon and a span of oxen. The first night

away they camped on Christmas Pass and, after dinner, made up the fire rolled themselves up in blankets and went to sleep under the wagon. Suddenly and silently a lion seized Teal by the foot and dragged him away. The native swarmed up a tree - he had a rifle but was too terrified to fire. The lion dragged Teal towards a high bank and a lioness sprang out of the grass giving the prey playful taps in cat-like fashion, and uttering little grunts of pleasure. The unhappy man's shrieks were heard for many minutes.

The next day Teal's head was found under a bank and part of his arm was lying close by. The lions were shot by a Dutchman soon afterwards.

Selous visited Umtali and sent the nurses a note to the effect that he would visit them as soon as he could get his shirt washed! At the end of September "Dr. Jim" (Jameson) had an interview with the nurses and a good deal of pent up irritation was vented on his head. Said the officer accompanying Jameson: "He went into that hut a man and came out a mouse". Jameson was too large a man to bear malice and from that date the Company took entire charge of the hospital.

The hospital had been opened on 22nd September and the first patient arrived on the 26th: an elderly man in the advanced stage of phthisis for whom the nurses could do little. His first meal was a huge plateful of not overfresh tinned lobster, virtually the only good available at the time as, when in Biera, the tins had been conveniently sized to make up the carriers' loads of whisky to the accepted weight.

On 8th October Bishop Knight-Bruce left to visit the remainder of the country between Umtali and Salisbury. Little did he think as he waved farewell that on his return he would find a little group of deserted huts and his holder, Wilkins, dead from fever.

The following day Rhodes crossed the border after a trying trip. He had started with two horse-drawn carts and riding animals. The horses turned out to be bad pullers and the poles of the carts were broken in the steep dongas. No sooner had the carts been abandoned than the horses carrying the utensils were eaten by lions - nothing remained but the pots, the pans and the hoofs.

Rhodes, 38 years of age and Prime Minister of the Cape, was soon able to exert his personal magnetism on the string of moaners who came to see him and the legend that Rhodes would "square" everything, including the tsetse fly, was confirmed. Rhodes also visited the Nurses and their patients and signed a cheque for £150.0.0.

Two visitors to the settlement, Theodore Bent and Charles Finlayson, have provided a description of Umtali in late 1891. On the

right of Fort Hill were the camp huts of approximately 200 Company Police, with the fort itself on the highest point of that eminence. On another rise was the hospital whilst to the east, on Sabi-Ophir Hill, were the huts of the original settlers. Further away was the Bishop's hut in the middle of the mission station. Immediately north of Fort Hill and across the stream was a collection of huts and stores : the butcher had, in his advertisement, called the dusty area between the buildings "Main Street". Old Angus, a sandy-haired little Scotsman, kept two huts : the first supplied a never-ending stream of whisky and gossip; the second was divided into three cells and called a hotel.

The officers' mess of the Company Police was furnished with loot taken from Macequece. When the Governor of that district came to pay an amicable visit he was seated on his own chairs, fed off his own plates and served with his own tinned meats. Portuguese politeness rose to the occasion and no remarks were made.

Also in the vicinity of the Police camp was the "reading room", a large square hut with the mud fallen off the walls, the sky visible through the roof and a floor of mud. The most recent newspaper was seven weeks old and the best chair was a bully-beef case. The room was also used as the officers' kitchen and there were always dirty plates on the ground and a fire in the centre. (The discovery of certain artifacts on Fort Hill recently - old plates, bottles, a cooking pot and a water purifier - suggest the likely situation of this building). The library was "destitute of the most ordinary books" but was "well supplied with fleas" which at night were reputed to drive the uninitiated out into the night "sobbing"!

It had become apparent however that the Penhalonga area was not suitable for the development of a major town : there was little level ground and the many mining claims limited expansion. There was no alternative but to move the settlement and, after the departure of Rhodes, Mr. Fienees with some of his Police and a number of natives, camped at the newly selected site six miles further west (the present site of Old Umtali) and began to build the police camp, huts for the nurses and a hospital.

In December 1891, the move was completed. As the main party reached the site the heavens opened and the wagon, some way behind, overturned on the slippery baks of a donga. Blankets were rescued from the swirling waters, the nurses wrapped themselves up, lit a fire ... and slept.

THE GOLD ROUTE TO MANICALAND

R. Plowes 2A

News of gold in Mashonaland interested many people in South Africa, but the road from Pretoria to the gold belt was long and hard. The best alternative was along an undeveloped, little known route from Beira to Umtali. The period 1888 to 1892 saw the main development of this route, with an increasing number of people using it. The following accounts of journeys made along this route help to describe the hardships and problems faced by the travellers.

In 1888 a gold miner from Barberton, Jeffreys, was appointed by his company to lead an expedition to Manicaland in order to investigate possibilities of goldmining there. After travelling by ship to Beira he met Baron Rezende, the Mocambique Company's representative, who decided to join the expedition. Beira at that time consisted of some hot huts built on a sand-bank, both mosquito and fly ridden.

The first job was to arrange to meet two hundred odd bearers up the Pungwe River in order to carry the sixty pound packs. This was duly done, and they departed on the newly-acquired paddle-steamer. They wanted to get the journey to Umtali over as soon as possible in order to miss the main rains whilst travelling. They sailed upriver to a large island where the bearers were supposed to be.

After waiting two weeks the party of 12 pushed on to a place named M'tanda Chiqua where they received a message that the bearers refused to join the party owing to a raid which Gungunyana was presently conducting in Manicaland. Gungunyana, the powerful Shangaan chief, periodically sent marauding parties to destroy crops and livestock of local chiefs in order to keep them in submission.

Rezende and Jeffreys decided to go to Manicaland to assess the situation, while the remainder of the party went to Gouveia village in Gorongoza to spend the wet season and await instructions.

With six available bearers, Rezende and Jeffreys made for the Humbe Mountains, next to which was a large kraal. They arrived there after a hot, rough journey and stayed for a few days. On Boxing Day they left amid pleas not to cross the nearby river that separated Gorongoza from Manica as they were likely to be killed.

Despite this warning, they continued in the direction of Macequece following game-paths between water-holes, as there was no track or path direct to Macequece. After making slow progress through the Chimoio Valley and across the Revue River, they eventually arrived at the old Fort of Macequece.

Soon after arrival a message was received promising that Gungunyana's men would not hinder the party in any way once it moved from Gouveia village

The rains set in shortly, and very little work could be done around the fort owing to this and the dense bush in the area. Mealie meal, the principle food, was very hard to come by after Gungunyana's raid and being confined to the fort for days on end made life very miserable. Their hardships were added to when both Rezende and Jeffreys contracted malaria and there was no quinine. After a slow recovery, amid these hardships, they began a march back to Beira three months later. Jeffrey was to return the following year and peg the "Penhalonga" and "Rezende" mines.

On September 12th, 1890, the Pioneer Column of the British South Africa Company raised the Union Jack in Salisbury. The company ordered an investigation of the Beira-Umtali route as a possibility for a transportation route. There were two reasons for this, the first being to find a cheaper way to transport supplies to Mashonaland, and the second to find a drier route for the heavy wagons, for during the wet season rivers were practically impassable.

Major Frank Johnson, Dr. Jameson and a B.S.A. Company trooper, Hay, obtained permission from Baron Rezende, at Macequece, to navigate the Pungwe. They sold their horses and proceeded to the river where they constructed and launched their Berthon collapsible boat. They found the river to be typical of Africa, hippo and crocodile basking on sandbanks of broad pools, whilst in other places, a ready jungle of water-weed and rushes obstructed their progress.

Fifteen miles downstream they reached the trading station of Sarmento, the place regarded as the head of the navigable stretch of the Pungwe. A hut was provided for them to sleep in by a coloured Portuguese official. This proved to be disastrous for not only did their hut get burned down, but practically the whole village was set ablaze as a result of Johnson upsetting a candle. They lost most of their possessions and were very unpopular until twenty gold sovereigns were produced.

The river was thereonwards perfectly navigable for their small craft, and they could concentrate on things other than saving themselves from drowning. The highlights of the trip were the shooting of an Egyptian Goose and a female buffalo. At night they slept on board the boat for fear of wild animals on the banks. Mosquitoes added to the discomfort of sleeping cramped up, especially in the swampy area near the sea where they would descend in a "humming blanket". During the day the sun was the curse and they had to keep pouring water over their

heads to avoid sun-stroke. They all suffered badly from sunburn, despite these precautions. They arrived safely in Beira however, and were soon bound for Cape Town aboard a steamer.

As a result of this expedition and the publicity it received in Cape Town, the Pungwe route was regarded as excellent for Mashonaland-bound supplies, despite it being very rough and undeveloped.

Bishop Knight-Bruce heard of the route and considered it ideal for the nurses that he wanted to send to Mashonaland. The nurses were Rose Blennerhasset, Lucy Sleeman and Beryl Welby.

After many delays they arrived in Beira aboard the "Tyrian". The 13th June, 1891, saw them onboard the "Shark", a Thames launch, destined for M'panda. To go up the Pungwe mouth one has to go with the tide, and it so happened that the tide was going in at about 4 a.m. that morning. The bay was full of mist but they soon sailed out of it only to find themselves grounded on one of the treacherous shifting sand-banks of the Pungwe. They were soon free of it and spent the morning watching animal-life on the banks. In the late afternoon they passed Neves Ferreira, a small Portuguese camp some fifteen miles from their destination, M'panda. Suddenly the boat's propeller jammed and with jerky movements they continued to M'panda, arriving there six hours later, to find their promised sleeping quarters occupied by three ill men.

They had to spend the night huddled in a corner of a dirty tent listening to lions and hyenas calling. The next day a hospital hut was erected to house the sick men and to allow the nurses their own tent. A message was received from Bishop Knight-Bruce advising them to hire bearers to carry them in Machillas to Umtali. A machilla is a hammock suspended from a pole and carried by bearers.

After their attempts to engage bearers around M'panda failed, they returned to Neves Ferreira to try for bearers there. When this also met with a negative result, they had to decide on whether to return to Beira or walk to Umtali with their few bearers carrying the packs.

They chose walking to Umtali as they realised how much they meant to Bishop Knight-Bruce. Many of the men at M'panda tried to dissuade them from undertaking the journey as the walk was too strenuous but on the 30th June they, Dr. Glanville and Mr. Sutton departed with the reluctant bearers for Umtali.

Walking was tiring on the rough, narrow paths that linked the various kraals and there was always the added danger of lion attack. Communication with the locals was very difficult as only a few could speak Portuguese and none could speak English.

The Beira-Untali Route 1890

Note:
Only main rivers shown

After two and a half days of walking through swamps, game-filled plains, stretches of sand and ten-foot high grass they arrived at Sarmento, 45 miles from M'panda. They stayed at Sarmento overnight and at ten o'clock the following day they arrived at the bearers' home-kraal. The bearers refused to budge from there that day and only after much persuasion did they agree to go on to Macequece the next morning.

A few days later, after much rough walking, they arrived at Chimoio, 70 miles from Umtali. Here all but four of the porters deserted them. They were in quite a predicament but it was eventually decided that the nurses with three bearers and Dr. Glanville would walk to Umtali while Mr. Sutton, would guard the stores with the remaining porter.

They set out on the 4th July and two days later reached Macequece after crossing a large swamp. This two day walk, they were told was a record. From Macequece a runner was despatched to Umtali to warn Bishop Knight-Bruce of their arrival.

A bad rocky path, hill after hill, valleys and gulleys, intense heat and no water made the walk to Umtali the worst of the trip. One of the sisters had a fever and was running a temperature of 105°F. Towards sunset a flag was spotted, it was that of Umtali (Old Umtali now). Half an hour of walking saw them meeting the Bishop and completing one of the most famous marches ever done by women in Southern Africa.

The route from Beira to Umtali was becoming more developed and so more used. This eventually led to the construction of a railway from Fontes ville to Chimoio in 1893. However, nearly two years before this, in late 1891, Charles Finlason, a journalist, had walked to Beira from Umtali on his return journey to South Africa.

The party left Umtali in the pouring rain with donkeys carrying the main load. Although it is only 18 miles from Umtali (Old Umtali) to Macequece, it seemed a great deal further with all the hills and valleys to cross. The day after leaving they made Macequece and crossed the Revue River. On finding how difficult it was to carry so many supplies on the few donkeys, they hired four bearers to carry fifty pound packs to M'panda.

At night they were constantly woken by red ants and mosquitoes biting them while during the day, swamps, high grass and the heat hindered walking. They passed an ox-wagon drawn alongside some trees after the oxen had all died from Tsetse bites. The owner was selling all the supplies in the wagon before moving on.

While crossing a river on a fallen log, Finlason slipped and was nearly taken by a crocodile. They lost a bearer to a lion when he foolishly went to collect water by himself after fresh lion-spoor had been seen.

The day after this incident they intended to reach Sarmento and therefore the leaders set a fast pace. Slowly the party broke up into small groups with some lagging and others pushing on ahead. This was extremely dangerous owing to the possibility of lion attack. Towards dusk the three in Finlason's groups began singing to drown their fears of attack. They reached the rest of the party at midnight and spent the remaining dark hours next to a roaring fire.

They awoke to find themselves within a few miles of Sarmento. Upon reaching the village many people took the opportunity of having some Portuguese wine. The result was numerous splitting headaches.

The next day they pushed on to M'panda. Finlason, after walking a few miles in a swamp, hired a dug-out canoe to ferry himself to M'panda.

From M'panda a sailing boat was chartered to take the group to Beira. Unfortunately they found themselves sailing against the tide when they neared the river mouth and they had to spend the night on the bank. The following day they reached Beira which they found to be extremely hot and boring. After a dull wait they boarded a steamer for Durban.

One of the most prominent features in the development of the Umtali-Beira route was the construction of the narrow gauge railway from Fontes Ville to Chimoio. This proved to be a great asset to travellers for no longer was there the expense or danger that one previously encountered. Goods were shipped up to Fontes Ville where they met the train for Chimoio. From Chimoio to Umtali the goods could be taken by mule. The line was later replaced by a standard gauge track and extended to Beira and Umtali.

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 Umtali Museum Society Newsletter No. 6.

COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

J.C. Barnes

Some notes from the Community Development Training Seminar held in the Small Lounge of the Cecil Hotel, 26-28th April, 1972.

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One of the unfortunate results of the manner in which Rhodesia was occupied by the Europeans was the development of a horse/rider relationship between the two main races : "I know what is good for you so you do what I say". The first attempts to overcome this attitude were associated closely with the planned progress of the African and it was done along three main lines:-

1. By example: examples were set for others to follow - the 'Master Farmer' scheme, demonstration plots carefully cultivated in African areas, or the influence of individuals trained at Domboshawa. This aspect was not a success in that the norms of tribal society acted against it. A Master farmer, for example, would be ostracised from society and regarded as distinctly 'peculiar'. As one African described it, whereas a European tries to keep up with the Jones and African keeps down with society.
2. Government -sponsored Projects: such as the building of dams, weirs and bridges. Because such projects were entirely government built the people neither respected nor maintained them
3. Legislation was introduced to control such aspects as destocking, soil conservation and land husbandry (combined in the Native Husbandry Act of 1951) but it merely aroused open antagonism and there was much wanton destruction.

These schemes failed basically because of their autocratic nature, because they were imposed from above; it was the Whitehead Government which introduced an alternative policy of Community Development. With the accession of the Rhodesian Front to power in 1962 it was neglected as something of a hot potato but in 1965 a Directive was issued from the Prime Minister's Office in which Community Development was reinstated as official government policy.

What is Community Development? Basically it is the development of the community by the community; people accept responsibility for development in their own area.

What are the main steps by which one introduces Community Development into an area?

1. Define the community.
2. Identify the leaders. Fortunately tribal society already has a leadership structure in the chief, headman and kraalheads.

Tribal Structure

PEOPLE

3. Clearly place with the people responsibility for their own development.
4. Educate the community : sell the idea, show its difficulties and its benefits, develop a plan of action.
5. Show the need for maintenance once the initial construction stages have been completed.

What is the difference between Tribal Trust Lands and African Purchase Area?

A Tribal Trust Land (or Native Reserve) is land held by the chief on behalf of his people. People can acquire rights to that land only if they pay allegiance to the chief.

The African Purchase Areas originated as a government idea to secure a stable, middle class type of person. The government advertises farms for purchase by suitably qualified Africans : those holding a Master Farmer Certificate and with sufficient capital, cattle and agricultural implements. For the first three years the occupant is inspected by government officials after which he is free to purchase the farm at a nominal fee.

Of Rhodesia's African population of five million, three million live in the T.T.L.'s and African Purchase Areas.

	Chiefs	Headmen
Rhodesia	250	400
Manicaland	30	50

TRIBAL TRUST LANDS IN MANICALAND

<u>T. T. L.</u>	<u>CHIEF</u>	<u>AREA IN HECTARES</u>	<u>POPULATION</u>	<u>NO. OF CATTLE</u>
Marange North	Marange	92.153	56,087	24,323
" South	"	118.00		19,041
Mutasa North	Mutasa	25.981	11,039	5,190
" South	"	19.782	9,112	6,725
Zimunya	Zimunya	10.766	10,526	8,594
Chinyauwhera	"	14.933	7,872	
Rowa	"	7,378	3,485	
Dora	"	11,330	1,722	3,345
Muromo	"	10,290	6,426	2,348
		310,613	106,269	59,566

Taken from a table drawn up by
Mr. D. Plowes, Ministry of
Internal Affairs. 14.1.72.

Areas of the Chief's Influence

Chief's Court (Dare)

Judicial CourtTribal Land AuthorityCouncil

(A traditional body
selected by the chief to
determine land policy)

(A European innovation.
Controls physical
progress : roads,
dips, bridges, etc)

Tribal Development
CommitteeCommunity Boards

The Councils and Community Boards, as the official bodies to run
local government in an area, need closer study.

The Community Board is an assembly of people to achieve something
that is of common interest to them. It is a loose body usually formed
for one project only (e.g. the bridge as seen by the History Society in
Umtasa North T.T.L. last year) after the completion of which it is
disbanded. Government will not give these boards money as they do
not have a proper accounting system, but they will make contributions
of material.

make contributions of material.

The Council is a more formal body established by legislation. The request to form a council must come from the people and if the District Commissioner considers such a council necessary the Minister of Internal Affairs will issue a warrant bringing that council into being and outlining its powers. The members of the Council are :

President: District Commissioner (advisory capacity only)
 Vice-President: Chief (advisory only but he does have a limited veto)
 Headmen (ex-officio)
 Elected members

A Chairman is elected out of their number.

The Council operates by means of committees which are formed to look after specialist services such as finance, health, education, public works.

The Council employs a Secretary (who is usually Treasurer as well) who normally has his 'O' levels and has completed a one year training course at Domboshawa. On him depends to a large extent the efficiency of the Council.

Where does the Council get its money?

1. Rates: if a rate of \$2.00 per man is imposed by the Council government will cancel the government tax for that area.
2. Government grants:-
 - (a) block grant - dollar for dollar for rates collected up to \$10,000.
 - (b) initial grant of \$1,500 to new councils.
 - (c) salary grants - to encourage the employment of properly qualified persons; e.g. nurses (50%)
3. Liquor undertakings - beerhalls are usually lucrative.
4. Fees, especially from schools and dips.
5. Local taxes, especially dog, bicycle and vehicle taxes.

The largest Council in Rhodesia, Gwanda, has an annual budget of over \$500,000 and employ three Secretaries. At present there are 148 Councils in Rhodesia and it has been estimated that about 200 are necessary.

Other Development Agencies

Young Farmers Clubs provide experience in committee work, book work and leadership as well as encouraging the African children to stand on their own feet. The Y.F.C. Organisation originated in America and Britain and came to Rhodesia in the 1950's primarily to the European

schools. Today there are 180 clubs in Manicaland of which only two are European.

Their activities are not necessarily agricultural : it is essentially only that they exhibit self-organisation. Some of the community demands satisfied by the Y.F.C. include stock fattening, vegetable production, contour ridging, catering (a majority of Y.F.C. members are girls) beadwork and matwork. A noteworthy project run recently was a loan provided by the Lions Organisation to a select Y.F.C. to purchase a beast which was then fattened and eventually slaughtered. The Lions were reimbursed and the Y.F.C. retained the profit.

The minimum age is 12 years and the nucleus is the school, but as many Africans leave school at an early age many Y.F.C's are centred on the kraals.

The Y.F.C. is not connected with government but it does receive the co-operation of many ministeries : education, Internal Affairs, Conex and Agriculture to name but a few. There are so many clubs that the following infrastructure (mainly voluntary) has been established to control them :

National Committee (in Salisbury)

 4 Provincial Associations

 District Committees
 (6 in Manicaland)

 Area Committees

The Provincial Committee employes a Youth Extension Assistant who spends his time touring the Province inspecting, advising and encouraging.

Other development agencies include:-

Women Clubs

Farmer's Co-operatives: approximately 300 in Rhodesia with over 30,000 members. Provide marketing and supply, housing and credit facilities .

Tilcor (Tribal Trust Land Development Corporation)

Tilcor was established by an Act of Parliament to foster development in the Tribal areas. Its funds came initially from a \$24m government grant but today 45% of its capital comes from outside government. Tilcor sponsors and develops enterprises in the Tribal areas, e.g. Kiteyo Tea Estates, the Chisumbanje Complex - the only proviso being that any venture into which it enters must be profit earning : this is no benevolent society. It has no shareholding : all profits are reinvested in Tilcor.

Problems of Implementing Community Development

The more obvious problems are those of persuading the Africans of the necessity for Community Development and of educating the Councils in committee procedure and financial know-how. A very pertinent problem however is that of co-ordination : virtually every government department is involved in Community Development, thus policy is inaugurated at the top by a Cabinet Co-ordinating Committee. A Provincial Committee meets three times a year with representatives from all ministeries and at District level a meeting is held monthly with attendance compulsory for all those involved.

UMTALI'S FIRST MINE : THE REZENDE

Jan Bekker

During the August holidays E. Smith, J. Heyns and myself spent three days working in the National Archives. The following is part of our research - the history of the Rezende mine, the first working gold mine in Manicaland.

Mr. James Henry Jeffreys was the first white man to discover the Untali gold fields. Having obtained a number of Mocambique Company concessions to peg claims in the Manica province, Jeffreys and the Baron de Rezende used their rights to peg the Rezende and Penhalonga mines in 1889.

The outcrop of the reef was covered with a large line of extensive ancient workings stretching from the western section of the mine to the Mutare river in the East. Portuguese travellers and missionaries record gold being worked near here by the natives in the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries, but no work appears to have been in progress when the European prospectors of the late 19th century arrived in the valley.

On the 14th September, 1890 representatives of the British South Africa Company made a treaty with Chief Mutasa, the local native chief. Manicaland including the Penhalonga valley came under British influence. The rights of the concession holders were still recognised and their Mocambique claims later repegged as Rhodesian ones. The Rezende concession was sold to the United Goldfields of Manica Limited who began developing the mine.

The Rezende concession contributed eight claims each 100m². The first work carried out by the first manager Mr. H.J. Hillary, was

sinking several adits and shafts. The reef varied from between 2ft. 6ins. to 3ft. in thickness and dipped northwards. Assays taken from this working showed considerably over 2oz.

By 1893 a splendid battery site had been secured and the proposed water race from the Umtali waterfall gave a clear 300 ft. fall and enough power to drive any number of stamps. Many thousands of tons of quartz lay on the surface which would pay the mill. 2000 ft. of tramway was completed and ten trucks were on their way to the mine. The property was being thoroughly and practically worked, but owing to the shortage of labour at this time the Rezende only worked day shifts.

Native labour and food became increasingly scarce and by 1895 the company's capital was badly depleted. In March, 1898, the company went into liquidation and a new company, Rezende Limited, was formed with a share capital of £150,000 of which £13,500 were issued to the B.S.A. Company in commutation of royalty.

In 1899 a 10 stamp mill, crusher, 1000 ton cyanide plant, two true vannors, a concentrator and other mining equipment arrived from England. The mill began running in July, the recovery from 313 tons of ore treated being 424 oz. of gold. On the 8th August a fire destroyed the mill house, seriously damaging the plant which was not all insured.

The mill started up again in 1900, the power coming from a plant on the Umtali river at the bottom of Penhalonga waterfall. During September the mill ran for 15 days and crushed 515 tons of ore. 422 tons were cyanide treated and the total fine gold recovered was 500 oz. The total value of the yield was approximately £2000.

1902 was a bad year for the Rezende. Timber was becoming scarce and from February till May all transport was stopped through cattle sickness. By 1904 the company was in financial difficulties and made a loss of about £5000 on the year. The cause of the loss was partly due to the fall in the grade of the ore and partly to the shortage of power to run the 20 stamp mill and the cyanide plant. In May, 1905 after much reconstruction a new company Rezende Limited, was formed. The mine was now to be jointly administered with the Penhalonga mine, which was to supply Rezende mine with power from its Odzani station.

Under the new directorship the Main Shaft was retimbered and the mill increased to 30 stamps. But the mill was only able to start operating in March, 1906, due to the lack of power before. Early in 1908 hardly enough ore could be found for the mill and working costs were

rising and profits falling. It was decided to cut expenses by reducing the staff and in October the mill stopped. In December an extraordinary meeting was held and the company went into liquidation.

Rezende Mines Limited, was formed on the 4th December 1908, with a capital of £70,000 in one pound shares. Much improvement was carried out on the mine without much processing being carried out - the mill only started operating again in October, 1909. The capital was increased in 1910, enabling the company to redeem practically all the debentures.

The Great War had a slight effect on the mine. Profits fell slightly in 1915 owing to increased costs imposed by the war.

In November 1917 it was decided to move the administration of the company from London to Salisbury. Sir Abe Bailey became chairman, and the London and Rhodesian Mining and Land Company Limited, secretaries and consulting engineers.

Immediately after the war an influenza epidemic broke out in the mining area. This greatly hindered operations as out of a staff of 1300 on the Rezende mine, three Europeans and 50 natives died while another 650 natives deserted.

Between 1909 and 1937 the working profit of the mine was £1,458,702, equivalent to 13s 6d. per ton while the average working cost, including development redemption of 3s. 6d. per ton, was 20s. 4d. per ton. Owing to the fact that the ore was becoming increasingly expensive to mine and because of consistent flooding in the lower levels the mine was later closed down. It has recently been re-opened and is again producing.

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THE LAST DAYS OF ROMMEL

J.M. Smith IIIA

General Erwin Rommel was 49 years old when he rocketed to fame in May 1940 as commander of the Seventh Panzer division during the German sweep across France. Two years later, when his Afrika Korps stood only 70 miles from Alexandria, his name was a household word all over the world. That was the year Hitler made him a Field Marshall and the British called him the ablest general of the war.

When the "Tommyes" of the British Eighth Army which opposed him in Africa spoke of doing a "rommel" they meant doing a superb job. His cunning and talent for improvisation earned him the title or nickname of "The Desert Fox". Once, hard pressed by the British he frightened them off by convincing them of his superior strength: knowing that everyday the R.A.F. photographed over the German lines, he ordered every available vehicle to drive the whole time for two days and nights, tracks over tracks, in the surrounding desert. The resulting photos, with added German propaganda, led the British into overrating the German forces, and they retreated rapidly.

Rommel had an air of quality about him. It was in the cocky set of his cap, it was in his peasantlike cunning. To his men, who saw him rising out of the turret of his tank in the front battle line, he was the god of battle.

"Stay close to me", he once said to one of his officers while they were under fire, "Nothing ever happens to me".

But something did happen to him in the end. What are the little known facts of his death? The official German story was that he died of injuries received when his command car was strafed near Livarot, south of Le Havre, at the time of the Normandy invasion. But the truth is far more dramatic and revealing.

It was during the losing battles of the African campaign that Rommel realized Hitler's contempt for the individual human being. Rommel knew that the campaign was lost beyond redemption, owing to the German lack of gasoline and the greatly reinforced British strength. He demanded that Hitler withdraw the German troops as the only means of saving the lives of thousands of men. Hitler replied excitedly: "Triumph or Death".

"I neither triumphed nor died", Rommel later commented dryly.

Before the surrender in Tunisia in May 1943, Hitler had ordered Rommel's return to Germany to become part of the Fuhrer's entourage so that he would not be identified with the defeat. The months that followed were bitter ones. Rommel had never joined the Nazi party was never decorated with the golden party emblem. And he had formerly ignored the wholesale killings, the slave labour, the concentration camps, the Gestapo terror in the occupied areas. Now he was horrified by what the Nazis did in the name of the German people.

"I conducted a clean war", he said, "but they soil my uniform". Later, when Hitler released his notorious order to shoot all the hostages at a ratio of 12 : 1, Rommel was one of the few German commanders who threw it in the wastepaper basket. What pained Rommel most was the realization that Hitler would drag all Germany into the abyss with him rather than give up.

To bolster the confidence of the German people and to impress the allies, Hitler assigned to Rommel the ground command of the anti-invasion forces in Normandy. The General soon foresaw that a full scale invasion could not be repelled with the meagre supply of equipment and troops at his disposal. In April, 1944, he conferred with General Karl Heinrich von Stulpnagel, military governor of France and a leader of the German resistance to Hitler, about ways and means of ending the war in the west at once and overthrowing the Nazi regime.

In the hope of gaining something a little better than the complete and unconditional surrender proclaimed as allied policy Rommel wished to offer an armistice to Eisenhower and Montgomery without the knowledge of Hitler. Its basis was to be the withdrawal of German troops behind the West wall. In return the allies were to stop bombing the German cities at once. In the east, however, the Germans were to continue fighting on a shortened front - Rumanica, Lemberg, the Vistula, Memel "in defence of Western civilisation". Rommel proposed to have Hitler siezed by reliable panzer units and tried before a German tribunal. He did not believe in making Hitler a martyr by killing him outright.

Following the successful allied invasion of Normandy, Rommel sent an ultimatum to Hitler in which he demanded the immediate opening of armistice negotiations.

On the evening of July 18, 1944, Rommel, returning from the front, reached the outskirts of Livarot. Suddenly two planes with British markings headed directly toward him. One, flying only a few yards above the ground, strafed the left half of the car. Rommel was knocked

unconscious and thrown out of the car. As he lay on the ground the second plane swooped down and opened fire. Rommel was so seriously wounded - a skull fracture, two temple fractures, a broken cheekbone, an injury to the left eye, concussion of the brain - that doctors doubted he would live.

This was the first of two severe blows to befall the anti-Nazi plot. The second came on July 20 "Operation Valkyrie", the conspiracy of German Army leaders and anti-Nazi civilians to assassinate Hitler (into the preparations for which Rommel had previously been drawn by Stulpnagel), mis-fired at the Fuhrer's Prussian headquarters, injuring 20 men and killing four. But Hitler miraculously escaped. Nazi revenge hunted down the known conspirators. Those who were caught were executed.

By the end of summer Rommel had made a brilliant recovery; except for a partial paralysis of his left eye, he was as good as new. On October 14, he rose early in his villa in Herrlingen, near Ulm, to meet his sixteen year old son, Manfred, who was arriving home for a brief army furlough. But another less welcome visitor was expected at noon that day. A telephone call the previous night had informed Rommel that General Wilhelm Burgdorf was being sent by the Fuhrer to discuss with him his "new command". The Marshall remarked to Manfred "Burgdorf's coming may be a trap".

At 12 o'clock General Burgdorf arrived, accompanied by General Ernest Maisel. Rommel, with his wife and son, greeted the visitors. They kissed Her Excellency's hand. There was the usual exchange of small talk, about the lovely weather and everyones health, including the Field Marshall's splendid recovery. Presently Frau Rommel and Manfred withdrew.

A little after one o'clock Rommel came up stairs to his wife's room. "What is the matter?" Frau Rommel exclaimed, alarmed by the look on her husband's face.

"In a quarter of an hour, I shall be dead," Rommel said absently as though tasting the words for their meaning.

He told her quickly: The testimony of Stulpnagel (who had been strangled after he blinded himself in a suicide attempt) had left no doubt about Rommel's participation in the July 20 plot. Hitler now gave him the choice between death by poison immediately or a trial before a Peoples' Court. The two Generals had made it quite clear that if

Rommel insisted on standing trial, reprisals would be taken against Frau Rommel and Manfred: if he let himself be poisoned, his family would be spared and would receive all honours and pensions due to the family of a German Field Marshall. The Fuhrer was determined to keep from the German people the fact that their most popular General had plotted to overthrow him and make peace. With ghoulish precision Burgdorf had outlined for Rommel the last details of the plan. On the drive to Ulm a poison would be given him. Within three seconds he would be dead. His body would be delivered to a hospital in Ulm. A message would go to the world that he had died suddenly from the after effects of his July 17 injuries.

In that upstairs room Rommel divulged details of the diabolical plan to two others - his aide, Captain Aldinger and Manfred. Then these three went downstairs. Rommel let himself be helped into his greatcoat, then put on his cap, a little jauntily as usual. Manfred and Aldinger handed him his gloves and baton. Then he walked out to the car where his assassins waited, and drove off.

In all the history of the Third Reich no scene shows more the absolute power on which Hitler thrived. Here was no poor helpless Jew in the hands of the Gestapo. Here was a German Field Marshall, baton and all the glory of the Army, a legend over all the world for his courage and cunning. Yet this man let himself be taken away to his death.

At 1.25 General Burgdorf and General Maisel delivered Rommel to the Hospital at Ulm. He was already dead. The physician proposed an autopsy, but Burgdorf quickly said "Berlin has arranged for everything".

Exactly what happened on that drive will probably remain a mystery forever. Burgdorf perished with Hitler in the cellar of the Reich chancellery. Maisel and the SS driver later insisted that they were made to leave the car for a moment and on their return found Rommel dying.

At the state funeral on October 18 the assembly, studded with Nazi chieftains and high officers behaved with sole decorum. Field Marshall von Runstedt delivered the oration in Hitler's place. Frau Rommel had refused Von Runstedt's arm and a nameless tension threatened to burst through the thin veneer of well-bred tact. Only a few of those present realised that they were attending the final act of a murder.
